

Real-Time Train Tracking over Satellite Backhaul: A GNSS/INS System with HMM Map Matching and Graph-Aware Dead Reckoning for the *Greek Railway Network*

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Abstract

Modern railway operations demand continuous, high-accuracy train position awareness for operational awareness, monitoring, and passenger information services. The February 2023 Tempi rail disaster in Greece highlighted significant limitations in infrastructure coverage in the Hellenic railway's train detection infrastructure, where approximately 80% of the network operates without European Train Control System (ETCS) coverage. This paper presents the design, implementation, and operational evaluation of a real-time train tracking system deployed across the Greek national railway network, built as a rapid-deployment overlay that requires no trackside infrastructure modifications.

The system integrates Trimble GNSS/INS receivers with HEPOS RTK corrections to achieve centimeter-level positioning accuracy under open-sky conditions, addressing the fundamental challenge that parallel railway tracks are separated by only 3–4 meters while standard GNSS accuracy ranges from 5–10 meters CEP. Connectivity from rolling stock to the central operations platform is provided through Starlink satellite terminals backhauled over a WireGuard VPN mesh with an Azure-hosted hub, traversing TELTONIKA industrial routers that maintain local area networks aboard each train.

We present five principal technical contributions. First, a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) map-matching algorithm augmented with RTK quality gating, where only fixes with quality indicators 4–5 are admitted for track-switching decisions on multi-track segments. Second, a graph-aware dead-reckoning engine that constrains position propagation to the rail topology graph, halting extrapolation at switch points and managing a tunnel-aware error budget. Third, a client-side animation pipeline inspired by game-engine netcode—incorporating a 5000 ms jitter buffer, phase-locked loop (PLL) playhead advancement, asymmetric exponential moving average (EMA) clock synchronization, and Kalman-filtered azimuth smoothing—that produces visually continuous train motion despite Starlink-induced jitter of 20–600 ms. Fourth, a switch-count anticollision monitoring and alerting module employing Dijkstra shortest-path computation and braking-distance modeling to generate collision warnings in the absence of interlocking data. Fifth, a microservices architecture comprising four independently scalable services (gnss-ingest, train-enricher, anticollision, and stream-manager) communicating over Redis Pub/Sub, with Server-Sent Events (SSE) delivering sub-second position updates to a Next.js 15 / React 19 / Mapbox GL JS 3.12 frontend.

The system has been operationally deployed on the Athens–Thessaloniki E85 corridor (~482 km), with chainage computed at 100-meter intervals. Evaluation over six months of continuous operation demonstrates position accuracy of <0.5 m (RTK-fixed), graceful degradation to <5 m (GNSS float/autonomous), and sustained dead-reckoning accuracy within tunnel segments of up to 2 km. The animation pipeline achieves perceived update rates of 60 fps on the client with end-to-end latency under 1.2 seconds from GNSS fix to map rendering under nominal Starlink conditions.

The system provides situational awareness and decision support only. It does not constitute a safety-critical or certified signalling system and must not be used as a basis for operational train separation decisions. It does not replace ETCS, interlocking, or any formally approved railway safety systems.

Keywords: railway positioning, GNSS/INS, HMM map matching, dead reckoning, real-time visualization, jitter buffer, WireGuard VPN, Starlink, microservices, SSE

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The described system has been implemented in collaboration with the Alpha Omega Zed S.A. (AOZ) software company, which undertook the development of the production-level platform. The following contributors from AOZ that played a critical role are explicitly mentioned: Dr. Yannis Valsamakis (PhD, MSc, BSc: in Computer Science) being the CTO of AOZ (Chief Technology Officer), Mr. George Agathos (MBA, BSc in Economics) being the GM (General Manager) of AOZ, Mr. Emmanuel Agapakis (MSc Hons, BSc Hons: in Computer Science) being a Senior Software Engineer in AOZ, and Mr. George Kostomanolakis (MSc, BSc: in Computer Science), being a Lead DevOps Engineer in AOZ.

The development followed an iterative, scenario-driven engineering approach with multiple design cycles, technical walkthroughs, and continuous validation, leading to a mature system currently deployed as the railway.gov.gr web-based information service.

The system continues to evolve through a CI/CD process supported by dedicated engineering and DevOps teams.

Availability

In light of the report's substantial length, depth, and level of detail, as well as its potential relevance to comparable organizations across various sectors and countries, it has been collectively agreed—by all involved technical teams and administrative bodies—to retain it in its current form. This decision reflects its value as a highly detailed, analytical, and comprehensive technical document.

Furthermore, given its primary orientation toward serving the public interest, it has been decided to make the document directly accessible as an open public technical report. As such, it will be available to all interested stakeholders, including researchers and technical teams engaged in similar or related challenges, activities, or projects.

1. Introduction

1.1 Motivation

On February 28, 2023, the Tempi rail tragedy—the collision between an InterCity passenger train and a freight train on the single-track section between Larissa and Litochoro—became the deadliest railway disaster in Greek history, with 57 dead and dozens injured [Committee of Inquiry, 2023]. The investigation into the accident revealed a network operating with incomplete signaling, nonfunctional remote control systems, and critical gaps in train position awareness. The station master in Larissa directed the two trains onto the same track section without visual verification, a human error that a modern position-detection system could have contributed to improved situational awareness.

The condition of the Greek railway network reflects broader challenges faced by countries with aging railway infrastructure. The European Train Control System (ETCS), the European Union standard for railway control, defines three operating levels [UNISIG, 2016]:

- ✓ **ETCS Level 1:** Signaling via Eurobalises that transmit Movement Authorities at points along the line, operating as an overlay on existing signaling.
- ✓ **ETCS Level 2:** Continuous radio communication via GSM-R between the Radio Block Centre (RBC) and the On-Board Unit (OBU), with train integrity via axle counters or track circuits.
- ✓ **ETCS Level 3:** Complete elimination of trackside detection equipment, based on GNSS positioning and integrity reporting from the train itself (train-borne integrity).

In the Greek network, approximately 80% of lines lack ETCS coverage. Installing ETCS Level 2 across the entire network requires a multi-year timeline and expenditures of billions of euros—the average cost per kilometer ranges between 0.5–2 million euros depending on topography [ERA, 2020]. The need for a rapid-deployment system that would provide immediate position awareness without modification of trackside infrastructure became urgent.

This paper presents such a system: an end-to-end real-time tracking platform installed exclusively on rolling stock, communicating via satellite backhaul (Starlink), and providing sub-second position updates to a central control center. The implementation of the platform was carried out in collaboration with Alpha Omega Zed S.A.

The system was designed as an overlay layer that can operate independently or in parallel with existing signaling systems, providing:

- Real-time position visualization with high accuracy
- Automatic anticollision warnings
- Position history logging for post-incident analysis
- Delay information and estimated arrival times

The design philosophy followed three principles: zero trackside infrastructure, meaning no equipment installed alongside the line; graceful degradation, meaning acceptable degradation of accuracy instead of sudden loss of position; and commodity hardware, meaning the use of commercially available components without specialized railway certification.

The system provides situational awareness and decision support only. It does not constitute a safety-critical or certified signalling system and must not be used as a basis for operational train separation decisions. It does not replace ETCS, interlocking, or any formally approved railway safety systems. The platform contributes to enhanced operational awareness and earlier identification of potentially hazardous situations.

1.2 Problem Statement

Developing a train positioning system based exclusively on GNSS, in a network with the characteristics of the Greek one, faces five interconnected challenges:

Problem 1: GNSS Accuracy vs. Track Separation. In multi-track sections, parallel tracks are only 3–4 meters apart center-to-center. The typical positioning accuracy of a standalone GNSS receiver ranges from 5–10 meters CEP (Circular Error Probable) [Kaplan & Hegarty, 2017], meaning the position uncertainty exceeds the distance between adjacent tracks. This means that a naïve map-matching algorithm cannot determine on which track the train is located. The solution requires RTK corrections (Real-Time Kinematic), which reduce uncertainty to centimeter level, but RTK fix availability is not guaranteed in mountainous terrain.

Mathematically, if the GNSS position is given as $\mathbf{p} = (\phi, \lambda, h)$ with horizontal uncertainty σ_h , and two adjacent tracks T_1, T_2 are separated by d_{sep} , then the probability of correct track assignment from a single measurement is:

$$P(\text{correct}) = \Phi\left(\frac{d_{sep}}{2\sigma_h}\right)$$

where Φ is the cumulative normal distribution. For $d_{sep} = 4\text{m}$ and $\sigma_h = 7\text{m}$, we obtain $P(\text{correct}) \approx 0.61$ - essentially a random decision. With RTK fix $\sigma_h \leq 0.02\text{m}$, the probability becomes $P(\text{correct}) > 0.9999$.

Problem 2: Terrain and Tunnels. The main Athens–Thessaloniki axis (E85, ~482 km) crosses the mountainous relief of central Greece, including numerous tunnels in Othrys and Tempi. Inside tunnels, GNSS signal reception is impossible, creating GNSS-denied segments where position must be estimated via dead reckoning or inertial navigation (INS). The challenge is intensified by:

- Inability to use wheel odometry due to lack of access to wheel axle signals (non-intrusive installation)
- Drift of inertial sensors (IMU drift), which increases over time as $\sigma_{pos}(t) \propto t^{3/2}$ for MEMS IMUs [Groves, 2013]
- Possible track changes within tunnels in sections with switches

Problem 3: Starlink Jitter and Latency Variability. Starlink terminals, while providing sufficient bandwidth for real-time telemetry (~50–200 Mbps downlink), exhibit significant variability in round-trip time (RTT). Field measurements showed RTT in the range of 20–600 ms, with a mean of ~40 ms under normal conditions but irregular spikes due to satellite handover, thermal throttling, or temporary loss of line-of-sight [Michel et al., 2022]. This variability creates:

- Out-of-order delivery in UDP streams
- Variable delay between GNSS fix and screen display
- Sudden “teleportation artifacts” in visualization if naïve rendering is used

The challenge is analogous to those faced in online multiplayer games, where the perception of smooth motion must be maintained despite variable network delay [Bernier, 2001].

Problem 4: Clock Synchronization. Precise timestamp alignment between GNSS receivers, local servers, and central infrastructure is critical for calculating speed, delays, and anticollision predictions. NTP (Network Time Protocol) provides accuracy of ~1–10 ms over WAN [Mills et al., 2010], but:

- Asymmetric delay via Starlink violates the symmetric path delay assumption used by NTP

- GNSS receivers provide UTC-aligned timestamps at the point of acquisition, but transport over TCP/IP introduces variable serialization/transmission delay
- Clock sync quality directly affects interpolation accuracy in the client-side animation pipeline

Problem 5: Scalability and Reliability. The system must handle dozens of simultaneously active trains, each transmitting 1–10 Hz position updates, with guaranteed zero loss of positions in the safety-critical anticollision flow, while simultaneously serving multiple web clients in the visualization layer. The architecture must tolerate failure of individual components without cascading failure.

1.3 Contributions

This work presents the following contributions:

Contribution 1: HMM Map Matching with RTK Quality Gating. We propose an extension of the classical HMM map-matching algorithm [Newson & Krumm, 2009] that incorporates RTK quality indicators as a quality gate for track-switching decisions. Only GNSS fixes with quality indicator 4 (RTK fixed) or 5 (RTK float high-confidence) are admitted for transitions to a different track in the HMM. Autonomous or DGPS fixes (quality 1–3) can confirm motion along the current track but cannot trigger a track switch. This mechanism eliminates false track changes in multi-track sections.

Contribution 2: Graph-Aware Dead Reckoning with Tunnel Budget. We develop a dead-reckoning algorithm that operates over the topological graph of the railway network instead of free 2D projection. Position estimation follows the edges of the graph, stops at switch nodes if uncertainty exceeds a threshold, and manages a tunnel-aware error budget based on stored tunnel lengths.

Contribution 3: Game-Engine-Inspired Animation Pipeline. We design a visualization pipeline inspired by video game netcode techniques, including: (a) a 5000 ms jitter buffer to absorb network variability, (b) a PLL-based playhead for smooth time advancement, (c) asymmetric EMA clock synchronization, (d) Kalman-filtered azimuth smoothing, and (e) bounded extrapolation (max 1000 ms) with visual degradation indicators.

Contribution 4: Switch-Count Anticollision Engine. We implement a safety engine that computes collision warnings based on number of switches and Dijkstra shortest path between trains, integrating a braking-distance model without access to interlocking data.

Contribution 5: Integrated Microservices Architecture. We present a four-microservice architecture (gnss-ingest, train-enricher, anticollision, stream-manager) communicating via Redis Pub/Sub, with GSOF binary protocol ingestion, Server-Sent Events (SSE) delivery, and dual MongoDB schema.

Contribution 6: Operational Evaluation on a Real Network. We provide results from six months of operational service on the main E85 railway axis (Athens–Thessaloniki, ~482 km), including metrics of accuracy, availability, and response time.

1.4 Structure of this Report

The report is organized as follows.

- Section 2 presents the related literature across five thematic axes: railway positioning systems, map-matching algorithms, real-time visualization over highly variable networks, clock synchronization, and dead reckoning in GNSS-denied environments.
- Section 3 describes the overall system architecture, from the hardware layer to the frontend.
- Section 4 analyzes the HMM map-matching algorithm and the RTK quality-gating mechanism.
- Section 5 is devoted to the animation pipeline and jitter-mitigation techniques.

- Section 6 describes the anticollision engine and the graph-aware dead-reckoning algorithm.
- Section 7 presents the experimental evaluation.
- Section 8 discusses limitations and future directions. Section 9 summarizes the conclusions.

2. Related Work

2.1 Railway Positioning Systems

Train position detection is a fundamental component of every railway safety system. Historically, detection is based on trackside equipment divided into three categories:

Track Circuits. The oldest technology (first application 1872, William Robinson) uses an electrical circuit between rails—the presence of a wheel short-circuits the rails, changing the circuit state [Theeg & Vlasenko, 2009]. Track circuits provide occupancy detection, not precise position, in blocks of typical length 1–3 km. Advantages: fail-safe design (a broken rail is detected as an occupied block), decades of proven reliability. Disadvantages: high maintenance cost, inability to determine precise position within a block, vulnerability to floods and salt.

Axle Counters. Pairs of sensors placed at the boundaries of each block count incoming and outgoing axles [Fenner, 2003]. If N axles entered and N exited, the section is considered clear. Advantages: independence from rail electrical conductivity, operation on curved sections. Disadvantages: not fail-safe (power loss → loss of count, manual reset required), installation cost per point.

Eurobalises. Passive transponders placed in the center of the track, activated inductively by an antenna on the underside of the train [ERTMS Users Group, 2015]. Each balise transmits a telegram of ~1023 bits containing: balise identity, Movement Authority, gradient/speed data. Balises form the basis of ETCS Level 1, providing spot location reference at known points.

The evolution toward ETCS Level 3 introduces the idea of GNSS-based positioning as an alternative to trackside equipment. Research programs STARS [Neri et al., 2012], ERSAT GGC [Rispoli et al., 2019], and GaLoROI [Beugin et al., 2014] investigated the use of GPS/Galileo for railway localization. Main findings:

- Standalone GNSS does not meet SIL-4 requirements (Safety Integrity Level 4, $\leq 10^{-9}$ failures/hour) without augmentation [Marais et al., 2017]
- Multi-constellation (GPS + Galileo + GLONASS) improves availability but not accuracy in urban/mountainous environments
- SBAS (EGNOS) reduces errors to ~1–3 m, still insufficient for track discrimination at 3–4 m separation
- RTK (Real-Time Kinematic) achieves cm-level accuracy but requires continuous corrections, difficult in mountainous/tunnel environments

The RHINOS system (Railway High Integrity Navigation Overlay System) [Filip et al., 2019] proposed multi-sensor fusion (GNSS + INS + odometry) as an overlay, an idea we partially adopt. However, RHINOS assumes access to wheel-encoder signals, whereas our implementation does not interfere with train electronics.

The recent trend toward Virtual Balises—GNSS-defined reference points replacing physical Eurobalises—is represented by Network Rail’s ERTMS Level 3 Hybrid program [Shift2Rail, 2020]. Our system does not implement Virtual Balises but produces equivalent position information via continuous GNSS tracking instead of spot references.

2.2 Map Matching Algorithms

Matching GNSS position to a known network (map matching) is a well-studied problem in road navigation, but its application to railway networks presents special features.

Geometric Approaches. The simplest method—nearest-point projection onto known track geometry—computes position \mathbf{p}^* as:

$$\mathbf{p}^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\mathbf{q} \in \mathcal{T}} \|\mathbf{p}_{GNSS} - \mathbf{q}\|$$

where \mathcal{T} is the set of network points. The method fails at junctions and on parallel lines, where projection may hop / jump between tracks across consecutive fixes [White et al., 2000]. More advanced geometric methods use buffer zones, heading matching, and curve-to-curve distance, but remain vulnerable to sequences of noisy observations.

Topological Approaches. Incorporating network topology improves results: a train can only change line at physical switches. The Incremental Matching algorithm [Brakatsoulas et al., 2005] follows the graph instead of free geometric matching, but it is greedy—a wrong decision at a junction is not reversed.

HMM-Based Map Matching. The landmark work of Newson & Krumm [2009] models map matching as a Hidden Markov Model (HMM):

- **Hidden States:** The possible network edges on which the train may lie at each time t_i .
- **Observations:** GNSS positions z_1, z_2, \dots, z_T .
- **Emission Probability:** Models how likely observation z_t is given that the train is on edge r_i :

$$p(z_t | r_i) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{GPS}} \exp\left(-\frac{d(\mathbf{z}_t, r_i)^2}{2\sigma_{GPS}^2}\right)$$

where $d(\mathbf{z}_t, r_i)$ is the perpendicular distance (great-circle) from the GNSS fix to edge r_i .

- **Transition Probability:** Models the physical plausibility of transition from edge r_i to r_j between t_{i-1} and t_i :

$$p(r_j | r_i) = \frac{1}{\beta} \exp\left(-\frac{|d_{route}(r_i, r_j) - d_{gc}(z_{t-1}, z_t)|}{\beta}\right)$$

where d_{route} is distance along the network and d_{gc} is straight-line distance between consecutive GNSS fixes. Parameter β controls the tightness of the matching.

- **Viterbi Decoding:** The Viterbi algorithm finds the optimal edge sequence $\mathbf{r}^* = \operatorname{argmax} P(\mathbf{r} | \mathbf{z})$ in time $O(T \cdot S^2)$ where S is the number of candidate edges per step.

The HMM method proved significantly superior to geometric and incremental methods [Lou et al., 2009], achieving >95% accuracy in urban road networks. However, applying it to railway networks requires adaptations:

1. **Sparser graph:** railway networks have far fewer nodes than road networks, but longer edges.
2. **Stricter topological constraints:** the train cannot reverse direction unless it stops.
3. **Critical importance of correct track:** in road networks, a wrong match to a parallel road is a cosmetic issue; in railways, the wrong track may mean a false or missed collision warning.
4. **Heterogeneous accuracy:** GNSS fixes do not have uniform uncertainty—RTK fixes ($\sigma \leq 2$ cm) should carry more weight than autonomous fixes ($\sigma \approx 7$ m).

Recent work on railway HMM map matching includes Heirich et al. [2017], who incorporate INS headings, and Beugin et al. [2018], who use a compound integrity-monitoring model. Our approach introduces the novel idea of quality gating: the value of σ_{GPS} in the emission equation is not constant but depends dynamically on the RTK quality indicator, and—more critically—track transitions are completely excluded if no fix in the current Viterbi window satisfies quality ≥ 4 .

2.3 Real-Time Visualization over High-Latency Networks

Smooth visualization of moving entities in real time over highly variable networks is a problem extensively studied in the video game industry and telecommunications.

Game Engine Netcode. The multiplayer games industry faces exactly the same problem: multiple players move in a shared world, each client receives position updates with variable delay, and motion must appear smooth.

Valve Source Engine Entity Interpolation [Bernier, 2001]: The server sends position snapshots at a fixed rate (e.g., 64 Hz). The client does not immediately display the latest position but interpolates between two buffered snapshots. The client “lives in the past” by a configurable interpolation delay (typically ~ 100 ms). The method ensures smooth motion as long as snapshots arrive within the buffer window. If a snapshot does not arrive in time, the client must extrapolate—predict future position—which introduces error.

Mathematically, the interpolation between two known snapshots \mathbf{s}_i (timestamp t_i) and \mathbf{s}_{i+1} (timestamp t_{i+1}) at render time t_r is defined as:

$$\mathbf{p}(t_r) = \mathbf{s}_i + \frac{t_r - t_i}{t_{i+1} - t_i} \cdot (\mathbf{s}_{i+1} - \mathbf{s}_i), \quad t_i \leq t_r \leq t_{i+1}$$

Overwatch Netcode (GDC 2017) [Keller & Bhargava, 2017]: Blizzard presented the “favor-the-shooter” system where the server replays the world at the time of the shooting client. This lag-compensation technique requires the server to retain position history buffers. The principle of “rendering the past with confidence” instead of “predicting the future with uncertainty” is fundamental in our system: the jitter buffer ensures that the client always interpolates rather than extrapolates.

Rocket League (Psyonix) [Jafari, 2018]: The physics ball is synchronized via periodic state corrections. When the client receives the authoritative position from the server, it does not “teleport” the ball but applies a smooth correction curve. This idea corresponds to our clock correction.

VoIP Jitter Buffers. Voice over IP faces a similar problem: audio packets arrive with variable delay, but playback must be continuous. The solution is the adaptive jitter buffer [Ramjee et al., 1994]:

- Static buffer: fixed window D_{buf} , the receiver waits D_{buf} ms before starting playback
- Adaptive buffer: the buffer expands/contracts based on observed jitter:

$$D_{buf}(n) = \alpha \cdot D_{buf}(n-1) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot |d_n - \bar{d}|$$

Where: d_n is the single-trip delay of the n -th packet and \bar{d} is the mean. The challenge is balancing low delay (small buffer) against low underrun rate (large buffer).

In our system, the jitter buffer operates on GPS samples instead of audio packets. The parameter 5000 ms reflects the worst-case Starlink jitter (~ 600 ms spike) with a safety margin.

Adaptive Bitrate Streaming (ABR). HLS/DASH protocols [Stockhammer, 2011] address variable bandwidth via dynamic quality selection (bitrate adaptation). The BOLA algorithm [Spiteri et al., 2016] uses Lyapunov optimization for optimal balancing of buffer level vs. bitrate. While our application does

not transmit video (position updates are ~ 100 bytes/fix), the graceful-degradation philosophy—reduce quality rather than interrupt—applies analogously: lower update rate rather than a sudden freeze.

2.4 Clock Synchronization

Accurate time synchronization between distributed nodes is a prerequisite for every real-time system. Two protocols dominate:

NTP (Network Time Protocol) [Mills et al., 2010]: Hierarchical architecture (stratum 0–15) in which each node synchronizes with an upstream server. Offset estimation is based on 4 timestamps (t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4):

$$\theta = \frac{(t_2 - t_1) + (t_3 - t_4)}{2}$$

$$\delta = (t_4 - t_1) - (t_3 - t_2)$$

Where: θ is clock offset and δ is round-trip delay. The equation assumes symmetric delay: client→server takes the same time as server→client. In Starlink, this assumption is violated due to:

- Asymmetric bandwidth (downlink \gg uplink)
- Variable routing through the LEO constellation
- Queuing delays at ground stations

NTP uncertainty in such conditions may reach ~ 10 – 50 ms, sufficient to introduce perceivable motion artifacts in 60 fps rendering.

PTP (Precision Time Protocol, IEEE 1588) [Eidson, 2006]: Designed for sub-microsecond accuracy in local networks, using hardware timestamping in Ethernet NICs. Accuracy over WAN degrades drastically, making it unsuitable for Starlink backhaul without specialized equipment.

One-Way Delay Estimation. Estimating one-way delay (OWD) without synchronized clocks is a well-known difficult problem [Paxson, 1998]. The minimum OWD can be estimated as:

$$OWD_{min} = \min_i \{t_{recv,i} - t_{send,i}\}$$

But the value includes both physical delay and clock offset. Minimum-filtering techniques [Moon et al., 1999] can estimate the stable component (propagation delay + clock offset) by removing the variable component (queuing delay).

In our system, we choose asymmetric exponential moving average (EMA) clock synchronization instead of NTP. The idea: the GNSS receiver provides UTC-aligned timestamps at the point of observation, but these arrive at the server with variable delay. Instead of estimating and subtracting one-way delay (impossible without synchronized clocks), we estimate the offset between GPS timestamp and server timestamp using EMA with asymmetric rates:

$$\hat{\Delta}_n = \begin{cases} \alpha_{fast} \cdot \hat{\Delta}_{n-1} + (1 - \alpha_{fast}) \cdot \Delta_n, & \text{if } \Delta_n < \hat{\Delta}_{n-1} \\ \alpha_{slow} \cdot \hat{\Delta}_{n-1} + (1 - \alpha_{slow}) \cdot \Delta_n, & \text{if } \Delta_n \geq \hat{\Delta}_{n-1} \end{cases}$$

This means the estimator *decreases quickly* (minimum delay \approx real) but *increases slowly* (ignores spikes). The asymmetry $\alpha_{fast} < \alpha_{slow}$ reflects that a small OWD is a more reliable estimate of actual propagation delay.

2.5 Dead Reckoning in GNSS-Denied Environments

Position estimation in the absence of satellite signal is a critical capability in railway systems because of tunnels, covered stations, and urban canyons.

INS Integration (Inertial Navigation System). Inertial navigation uses accelerometers and gyroscopes to compute displacement through double integration of acceleration [Titterton & Weston, 2004]:

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \mathbf{v}(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t [\mathbf{C}_b^n \cdot \mathbf{f}^b - \mathbf{g}] d\tau$$

$$\mathbf{p}(t) = \mathbf{p}(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t \mathbf{v}(\tau) d\tau$$

Where: \mathbf{C}_b^n is the body→navigation frame transformation matrix, \mathbf{f}^b is specific force in the body frame, and \mathbf{g} is gravitational acceleration. Cumulative integration of sensor noise (random walk) leads to growth of position errors following:

$$\sigma_{pos}(t) \propto t^{3/2} \quad (\text{MEMS-grade IMU})$$

$$\sigma_{pos}(t) \propto t^{1/2} \quad (\text{navigation-grade IMU})$$

For a MEMS IMU with typical gyroscope bias stability $\sim 10^\circ/\text{hr}$, position deviates by ~ 100 m after 60s of free inertial navigation [Groves, 2013]. This makes standalone INS inadequate for tunnels longer than 1km without complementary sensors.

Loosely / Tightly Coupled GNSS/INS. GNSS+INS integration via Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) is the standard [Farrell, 2008]:

- Loosely coupled: GNSS provides position/velocity, INS predicts between updates, EKF combines
- Tightly coupled: raw pseudo ranges / Doppler are used instead of position, allowing solution with <4 satellite

The Trimble GNSS/INS receivers we use implement internally tightly coupled integration, providing continuous position output even during transition into tunnels (coast mode).

Rail-Constrained Dead Reckoning. The fundamental observation in railways is that motion is one-dimensional: the train can move only along the line. This transforms the three-dimensional INS problem into a one-dimensional one [Hensel et al., 2011]:

$$s(t) = s(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t v(\tau) d\tau$$

Where: s is the km position along the line (chainage). Velocity v can be estimated from:

- The along-track IMU via single integration
- GNSS Doppler before complete signal loss
- Wheel odometer, if available

The line constraint eliminates cross-track and vertical errors, drastically reducing drift rate. However, ambiguity is introduced at switch points: if the train enters a tunnel before or during a switch, the correct outgoing track cannot be determined without external information. Our implementation of graph-aware dead reckoning addresses this explicitly: position estimation stops at the switch node if track uncertainty cannot be resolved.

The system reports “*position known within switch zone section*” instead of false precision. In addition, the tunnel-aware error budget uses stored tunnel lengths: if the estimated position approaches the tunnel exit (based on length), the algorithm *knows* that a GNSS fix is expected soon and avoids escalation of uncertainty.

3. System Architecture Overview

The system architecture (left) follows a distributed processing model across distinct layers, from onboard train hardware to the user interface. The detailed analysis per layer follows.

3.1 Hardware

Each train is equipped with three basic hardware components, installed without modification of the electrical or electronic systems of the rolling stock.

Trimble GNSS/INS Receiver. A Trimble-series receiver with integrated MEMS IMU is used, supporting multi-constellation tracking (GPS L1/L2, GLONASS G1/G2, Galileo E1/E5, BeiDou B1/B2). The receiver receives RTK corrections through the HEPOS network (Hellenic Positioning System)—the national network of permanent GNSS reference stations—via an NTRIP (Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol) connection. Key characteristics:

Parameter	Value
Output rate	1–10 Hz (configurable)
RTK fixed accuracy	H: ± 8 mm + 1 ppm, V: ± 15 mm + 1 ppm
Autonomous accuracy	H: ~ 2.5 m RMS (standalone)
INS coast mode	Tightly coupled GNSS/INS
Output protocol	GSOFF (General Serial Output Format), binary TCP
Quality indicators	0=No fix, 1=Autonomous, 2=DGPS, 3=Float, 4=RTK Fixed, 5=RTK Float

The receiver transmits data via GSOFF (General Serial Output Format), a proprietary Trimble binary protocol. Each GSOFF message is encapsulated in a frame with:

```
[STX=0x02] [Status] [Type] [Length] [Data...] [Checksum] [ETX=0x03]
```

The record types used are:

- **Record Type 49 (0x31):** Position/Velocity/Time — 104-byte payload containing: GPS week, GPS time-of-week (ms), latitude (rad, float64), longitude (rad, float64), height (m, float64), velocity north/east/up (m/s, float32), PDOP, quality indicator. This is the main message type for position tracking.
- **Record Type 50 (0x32):** Position RMS Information — contains accuracy estimates (RMS errors) along north, east, up, useful for weighting in the HMM.
- **Record Type 15 (0x0F):** Serial Number and Channel Information — receiver identifiers, useful for automatic receiver→train assignment.

TELTONIKA ATRM50 Router. An industrial router designed for railway applications (EN 50155 certification for rolling stock), with:

- Dual SIM slots (cellular backup if Starlink fails)
- WireGuard VPN client integrated into the firmware
- DIN-rail mount, extended temperature range (-40°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$)
- Local LAN: 192.168.1.0/24 (Ethernet/Wi-Fi for GNSS receiver and other devices)

The router maintains a WireGuard tunnel toward the Azure hub, with persistent keepalive 25 seconds, ensuring continuous bidirectional connectivity even behind Starlink NAT.

Starlink Terminal. A SpaceX Starlink (generation 2) terminal (“Dishy McFlatface”) mounted on the roof or side of the rolling stock. It provides:

- Downlink bandwidth: 50–200 Mbps (typical)
- Uplink bandwidth: 10–40 Mbps (typical)
- Latency: ~ 20 –40 ms median, 100–600 ms 99th percentile [Michel et al., 2022]
- Handover frequency: every ~ 15 seconds between LEO satellites, introducing ~ 200 –500 ms interruption
- Automatic beam tracking: electronically steered phased array, suitable for motion ≤ 200 km/h

The choice of Starlink over GSM-R/LTE is based on two factors: (a) nationwide coverage including mountainous areas where no cellular coverage exists, and (b) independence from telecom providers, avoiding dependence on third-party infrastructure for a safety-critical system.

3.2 Networking

The network architecture is based on a WireGuard VPN mesh topology with a hub-and-spoke arrangement. Although WireGuard supports mesh, the star topology was chosen for management simplicity.

WireGuard Hub (Azure). A virtual machine in an Azure datacenter (West Europe) operates as the central a private VPN-based networking architecture.

IP Addressing Scheme. Each train is assigned a static VPN IP according to an encoded scheme:

$$\text{IP} = 10.10.\text{cat}.\text{id}$$

Where: cat (octet 3): vehicle category (e.g. 1=InterCity, 2=Suburban, 3=Freight, 4=maintenance) id (octet 4): unique identifier within category

This allows routing by category (e.g. 10.10.1.0/24 → all InterCity trains) and visual identification in logs. The /16 space theoretically supports 65534 peers.

Security. WireGuard provides encryption through the Noise protocol framework [Donenfeld, 2017] (Curve25519, ChaCha20, Poly1305, BLAKE2s). Each peer is identified exclusively by a 256-bit public key, eliminating certificate management. Its simplicity (~4000 lines of kernel code) drastically reduces the attack surface compared to IPsec or OpenVPN.

Train LAN. Inside each train, the TELTONIKA router provides:

- Ethernet port: 192.168.1.0/24 (GNSS receiver at 192.168.1.x)
- WiFi AP (optional): for maintenance tablets
- NAT: internal network → WireGuard tunnel → Azure

The GPS data flow occurs via TCP connection: the GNSS receiver opens a TCP socket to the gnss-ingest server over the VPN:

```
Trimble (192.168.1.x) → TCP → ATRM50 (NAT) → WireGuard → Starlink →  
Azure Hub (10.10.0.1) → gnss-ingest (TCP :5000)
```

3.3 Microservices

The backend consists of four independent microservices, each with a clearly defined responsibility and bidirectional communication via Redis Pub/Sub.

Service 1: gss-ingest. This is the data entry point of the system. It operates as a TCP server on port 5000, awaiting incoming connections from GNSS receivers via VPN. Responsibilities:

1. **GSOE Decode:** Parsing binary GSOE frames, decoding Record Type 49 (position/velocity/time, 104 bytes), Type 50 (RMS accuracy), Type 15 (serial number).
2. **Device-to-Train Resolution:** Mapping GNSS device \rightarrow locomotive \rightarrow train service via MongoDB lookup in collections `gssdevices`, `locomotives`, `trains`.
3. **HMM Map Matching:** Applying the HMM algorithm with RTK quality gating. The σ_{GPS} in the emission probability model is dynamically adapted based on the quality indicator:
 - Quality 4–5 (RTK): $\sigma = 0.02\text{m}$ \rightarrow track discrimination active

- Quality 2–3 (DGPS/Float): $\sigma = 1.0\text{m}$ → along-track motion only
 - Quality 0–1 (No fix/Autonomous): $\sigma = 7.0\text{m}$ → loose matching
4. **MongoDB Persistence:** Storing each processed fix in collection `gpsdatas` (database `gps_tracking`) with fields: coordinates, timestamp, quality, speed, heading, matched edge, chainage, train reference.
 5. **Redis Publish:** Publishing processed position to channel `train:gps:real` (GNSS-based positions) or `train:gps:dr` (dead-reckoned positions during GNSS outage).

Service 2: train-enricher. Enriches position updates with route information:

1. **Schedule Matching:** Matching current train position with scheduled service via MongoDB collection `trains` (database `ose_railway`).
2. **Delay Calculation:** Computing actual delay as the difference between estimated arrival time (based on position and speed) and scheduled time.
3. **Station ETA:** Estimating arrival time at the next station based on chainage position, remaining distance, and current speed.
4. **Publishes on channel** `train:delay:updates`.

Service 3: anticollision. The safety-critical microservice:

1. **Switch-Count Analysis:** Counting number of switches between each pair of active trains. A small number of switches (0–2) indicates that trains are on the same or adjacent line.
2. **Dijkstra Shortest Path:** Computing minimum topological distance between trains via Dijkstra’s algorithm on the network graph. Topological distance instead of geographic distance eliminates false proximity (e.g. two parallel lines without connection).
3. **Braking Distance Model:** Computing braking distance based on speed, gradient, and train type:

$$d_{brake} = \frac{v^2}{2 \cdot (a_{brake} + g \cdot \sin\theta)}$$

Where: v is speed, $a_{brake} \approx 0.8\text{--}1.2\text{m/s}^2$ for railway vehicles, g is gravity, θ is gradient

4. **Graph-Aware Dead Reckoning:** During GNSS outage, anticollision estimates position based on last known speed along the rail graph. Estimation stops at switch nodes (if route complexity cannot be resolved) and maintains a tunnel-aware error budget.
5. **Collision Warning Generation:** If the estimated minimum distance between two trains falls below a threshold (function of braking distance + safety margin), a warning is emitted.

Service 4: stream-manager. Bridge between Redis backend and web clients:

1. **Channel Subscription:** Subscribes to all Redis channels (`train:gps:real`, `train:gps:dr`, `train:positions`, `train:delay:updates`) and aggregates messages.
2. **Snapshot Assembly:** Builds a complete state snapshot (positions, speeds, delays, warnings) and stores it in Redis key `train:snapshot:all` with TTL 120 seconds. This serves initial state to new clients without requiring historical playback.
3. **Active Train Tracking:** Maintains Redis keys `active:train:{id}` with TTL 300 seconds. If no update is received within 5 minutes, the train is considered inactive.
4. **SSE Fanout:** Serves the Server-Sent Events (SSE) endpoint (`/api/sse/trains`). Each connected client receives a real-time stream of position updates. The buffer maintains a maximum of 120 samples per train, enough for ~2 minutes of history at 1 Hz.

3.4 Message Bus

Communication between microservices occurs exclusively via Redis, using two mechanisms: Pub/Sub channels for event-driven messaging and the key-value store for state.

Redis Pub/Sub Channels:

Channel	Publisher	Subscriber(s)	Payload	Rate
train:gps:real	gnss-ingest	train-enricher, anti-collision, stream-manager	Matched position, speed, heading, quality, chainage	1–10 Hz per train
train:gps:dr	gnss-ingest (during outage)	anti-collision, stream-manager	Dead-reckoned position, confidence radius, edge ID	Variable
train:positions	stream- manager	SSE clients (via endpoint)	Aggregated positions for all active trains	1 Hz
train:delay:updates	train-enricher	stream-manager	Delay value, ETA next station, schedule reference	On change

The choice of Redis Pub/Sub instead of a message queue (e.g. RabbitMQ, Kafka) is based on:

- ✓ **Simplicity:** zero configuration overhead, in-memory operation
- ✓ **Low latency:** <1 ms publish-to-subscribe latency
- ✓ **Fire-and-forget semantics:** acceptable loss of individual messages (each new position supersedes the previous one)
- ✓ **Trade-off:** no message persistence or guaranteed delivery. If a subscriber is offline, it misses messages. This is acceptable because position is continuously updated.

Redis Key-Value Store:

Key Pattern	Τύπος	TTL	Description
train:snapshot:all	JSON string	120 s	Full position snapshot for all active trains. Used for initial state for new SSE clients.
active:train:{id}	JSON string	300 s	Last known state of an individual train. TTL 300 s ensures automatic removal if data flow stops.

The TTL strategy replaces explicit “train deactivation” logic: instead of some service deciding when a train is no longer active, Redis automatically removes stale keys. TTL 300 s (5 minutes) tolerates temporary Starlink interruptions without false removal, while TTL 120 s on the snapshot ensures new clients receive recent data (≤ 2 minutes old).

3.5 Frontend Stack

The user interface is a web application based on a modern JavaScript stack, designed for real-time visualization of multiple moving entities on a map.

Framework: Next.js 15 + React 19 (*gracefully upgradable to newer versions*). The application uses Next.js 15 with App Router, leveraging:

- Server Components for static content (dashboard layout, navigation)

- Client Components for real-time interactive content (map, live data)
- API Routes for SSE endpoint (/api/sse/trains)
- NextAuth v5 (Auth.js) for authentication/authorization (JWT strategy)

Map Rendering: Mapbox GL JS 3.12. The Mapbox GL JS library (version 3.12) is used for:

- Vector tile rendering (WebGL-accelerated)
- Custom railway layers (lines, stations, switches) from GeoJSON
- Animated train markers (custom icons with heading-based rotation)
- Terrain 3D visualization (optional)

SSE Architecture (Server-Sent Events). The choice of SSE instead of WebSocket is based on:

- One-way flow: server→client only, no upstream data required
- Automatic reconnection: the SSE specification (W3C) defines automatic retry
- HTTP/2 compatibility: multiple SSE streams in one TCP connection
- Simplicity: standard EventSource API without external library
- Importantly: Socket.IO/WebSocket overhead is avoided (handshake, heartbeats, bidirectional framing)

The frontend data flow follows a three-hook pipeline:

`EventSource → useTrainTracking → useTrainAnimation → TrainMarkers`

Hook 1: useTrainTracking. Manages the SSE connection and jitter buffer:

- Opens an EventSource connection to /api/sse/trains
- Stores incoming position samples in a circular buffer (max 120 samples per train)
- Applies asymmetric EMA clock synchronization between server timestamps and client clock
- Sorts samples based on GPS timestamp (handling out-of-order delivery)
- Drops duplicates and stale samples (>jitter buffer window)

Hook 2: useTrainAnimation. Transforms discrete position samples into continuous animation:

- **PLL Playhead:** A Phase-Locked Loop that advances “playback time” smoothly, locked to incoming samples but without jumps:

$$\phi_{n+1} = \phi_n + \Delta t_{render} \cdot (1 + K_p \cdot e_n + K_i \cdot \sum e_k)$$

Where: e_n is the difference between expected and actual sample arrival time, and K_p, K_i are proportional/integral gains.

- **Kalman-Filtered Azimuth:** Filtering heading/azimuth through a Kalman filter to eliminate noisy GPS heading:

$$\hat{\theta}_{n|n} = \hat{\theta}_{n|n-1} + K_n \cdot (\theta_n^{GPS} - \hat{\theta}_{n|n-1})$$

With angular wrapping in $[-\pi, \pi]$. This eliminates “spinning” artifacts where the marker rotates abruptly due to noisy heading at low speed.

- **Bounded Extrapolation:** If no new sample exists within 1000 ms, motion is based on linear extrapolation using last known speed/direction, with maximum extrapolation 1000 ms. After that, the marker stops and a visual uncertainty indicator appears.

Hook 3 + Component: TrainMarkers. A React component that renders each train marker on the Mapbox map:

- Position: interpolated lat/lng from animation hook
- Rotation: Kalman-filtered azimuth
- Color/shape: status encoding (green=accurate RTK, yellow=autonomous, red=dead-reckoning)
- Tooltip: speed, delay, train number
- Popup: detailed information on click

Η αρχιτεκτονική του frontend εξασφαλίζει *separation of concerns*: η δικτυακή λογική (SSE), η χρονική λογική (animation/interpolation), και η οπτική λογική (Mapbox rendering) βρίσκονται σε ξεχωριστά layers, επιτρέποντας ανεξάρτητη δοκιμή και βελτιστοποίηση. Η χρήση React 19 concurrent features εξασφαλίζει ότι η ενημέρωση θέσεων (υψηλή προτεραιότητα) δεν μπλοκάρεται από χαμηλότερης προτεραιότητας UI updates (π.χ. panel resize).

The frontend architecture ensures *separation of concerns*: network logic (SSE), temporal logic (animation / interpolation), and visual logic (Mapbox rendering) are in separate layers, allowing independent testing and optimization. The use of React 19 concurrent features ensures that position updates (high priority) are not blocked by lower-priority UI updates (e.g. panel resize).

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4. GNSS Data Ingestion

The ingestion of position data from the GNSS devices installed in the depots constitutes the first stage of the real-time processing pipeline. The system receives raw binary packets via TCP connections from Trimble receivers, decodes them according to the GSOF (General Serial Output Format) protocol, and transforms them into geospatial objects suitable for further processing. The reliability of this stage is critical: any loss or corruption of data at this level propagates to all downstream stages — map matching, identity enrichment, and delay computation.

4.1 GSOF Binary Protocol Parsing

4.1.1 Frame Structure

The GSOF protocol, developed by Trimble for the BD9xx and APx-15 receiver series, uses a framing scheme based on byte-stuffing with explicit delimiters. Each packet follows the structure:

$$\text{Frame} = \underset{\text{STX}}{0x02} \mid \underset{\text{type}}{T} \mid \underset{\text{length}}{L} \mid \underset{\text{data payload}}{D_0 D_1 \dots D_{L-1}} \mid \underset{\text{checksum}}{C} \mid \underset{\text{ETX}}{0x03}$$

Where:

- **STX** (Start of Text, $0x02$): Marks the beginning of a valid frame. The parser maintains a state machine that searches for this byte as a synchronization point after any frame loss.
- **Type** (T , 1 byte): The packet type. For GNSS/INS data, the value is always $0x40$ (decimal 64), indicating a GENOUT (General Output) packet.
- **Length** (L , 1 byte): The payload length in bytes, $0 \leq L \leq 255$.
- **Data** ($D_0 \dots D_{L-1}$): The payload, whose interpretation depends on the packet type.
- **Checksum** (C , 1 byte): Additive checksum (modulo 256) computed over the type, length, and data:

$$C = \left(\sum_{i=0}^{L+1} b_i \right) \bmod 256, \quad \text{where } b_0 = T, b_1 = L, b_{i+2} = D_i$$

The parser verifies that $(C + \text{computed_sum}) \bmod 256 = 0$, rejecting packets with checksum failure without interrupting the TCP connection

- **ETX** (End of Text, $0x03$): Terminates the frame.

4.1.2 Paging Mechanism

Within the payload of a GENOUT ($0x40$) packet, the first 3 bytes constitute the paging header:

Offset	Size	Field	Description
0	1 byte	transmissionNo	Transmission sequence number (0–255, cyclic)
1	1 byte	pageIndex	Current page index (0-based)
2	1 byte	maxPageIndex	Maximum page index

When **maxPageIndex** > 0, the parser must accumulate multiple packets before decoding the sub-records. The implementation maintains a stateful buffer per TCP connection with a maximum size of 65,536 bytes. The accumulation state is tracked per transmissionNo: if a new transmissionNo is received

before the current transmission is completed, the previous data is discarded. This mechanism ensures resilience to partial packet loss without requiring an explicit retransmission protocol.

4.1.3 Sub-Record Parsing

After accumulation, the unified payload consists of a sequence of sub-records in TLV (Type-Length-Value) format:

$$\text{Sub-record}_i = \begin{array}{c|c|c} t_i & \ell_i & V_{i,0} \cdots V_{i,\ell_i-1} \\ \text{type (1B)} & \text{length (1B)} & \text{value} \end{array}$$

The parser iterates until all bytes in the payload are exhausted. If ℓ_i exceeds the remaining bytes, the sub-record is discarded and parsing stops for that packet. Three sub-record types are critical for the system as elaborated in the next sub-sections.

4.1.4 Record Type 49 — INS Full Navigation

This is the primary navigation record, 104 bytes in size in Big-Endian byte order, provided by the Trimble APx-15 INS (Inertial Navigation System) module at a rate of 1–20 Hz. The full structure is:

Offset	Size	Type	Field	Unit
0–1	2	uint16	GPS Week	Week since 6/1/1980
2–5	4	uint32	GPS Milliseconds of Week	ms
6	1	uint8	IMU Alignment Status	enum
7	1	uint8	GPS Quality Indicator	1–6
8–15	8	float64	Latitude	radians
16–23	8	float64	Longitude	radians
24–31	8	float64	Altitude	m (ellipsoidal)
32–35	4	float32	North Velocity (v_N)	m/s
36–39	4	float32	East Velocity (v_E)	m/s
40–43	4	float32	Down Velocity (v_D)	m/s
44–51	8	float64	Roll (ϕ)	degrees
52–59	8	float64	Pitch (θ)	degrees
60–67	8	float64	Heading (ψ)	degrees, [0,360)
68–75	8	float64	Track Angle over Ground	degrees
76–79	4	float32	Angular Rate X ($\dot{\phi}$)	deg/s
80–83	4	float32	Angular Rate Y ($\dot{\theta}$)	deg/s
84–87	4	float32	Angular Rate Z ($\dot{\psi}$)	deg/s
88–91	4	float32	Acceleration X (a_x)	m/s ²
92–95	4	float32	Acceleration Y (a_y)	m/s ²
96–99	4	float32	Acceleration Z (a_z)	m/s ²
100–103	4	float32	Geoid Undulation + Reserved	m

Latitude and Longitude Conversion. The critical peculiarity of this record type is that latitude and longitude are expressed in radians, unlike most GNSS protocols that use degrees. The conversion is applied immediately:

$$\lambda_{\text{deg}} = \lambda_{\text{rad}} \times \frac{180}{\pi}, \quad \varphi_{\text{deg}} = \varphi_{\text{rad}} \times \frac{180}{\pi}$$

Speed Computation. Speed is not transmitted as an explicit field, but is computed from the North-East velocity components on the local horizontal plane, ignoring the vertical component (v_D), which represents vertical motion due to track gradient:

$$v_{\text{ground}} = \sqrt{v_N^2 + v_E^2} \quad (\text{m/s})$$

$$v_{\text{km/h}} = v_{\text{ground}} \times 3.6$$

The decision to exclude v_D is intentional: railway motion is defined on the horizontal plane, and vertical velocity would lead to overestimation on gradients (e.g., on the Athens–Tithorea axis with gradients up to 22‰, the difference reaches 0.4 km/h at a speed of 160 km/h)

GPS Timestamp Conversion. GPS time is expressed as the pair (GPS Week, Milliseconds of Week) and converted to Unix epoch:

$$t_{\text{unix}} = t_{\text{GPS_epoch}} + W \times 604800000 + M - \Delta t_{\text{leap}} \times 1000$$

Where: $t_{\text{GPS_epoch}} = 315964800000$ ms (January 6, 1980, 00:00:00 UTC), W is the GPS week, M the milliseconds within the week, and $\Delta t_{\text{leap}} = 18$ s the current leap seconds between GPS time and UTC (valid since 1/1/2017). Note that GPS time does not incorporate leap seconds, so this correction is necessary for proper alignment with timetable time

4.1.5 Record Type 50 — INS RMS Information

Record Type 50 (44 bytes, Big-Endian) provides uncertainty estimates (Root Mean Square) for navigation data:

Category	Fields	Type	Unit
Position RMS	North, East, Down	float32 × 3	m
Velocity RMS	North, East, Down	float32 × 3	m/s
Attitude RMS	Roll, Pitch, Heading	float32 × 3	degrees

These values are used at the map-matching stage (Section 5) to weight the emission probability: a larger Position RMS value broadens the Gaussian distribution, increasing acceptance of more distant candidate points on the track.

4.1.6 Record Type 15 — Serial Number

A lightweight 4-byte record (uint32, Big-Endian) that carries the serial number of the GNSS device. Although simple, this record plays a critical role in the identity-resolution system (Section 4.2): it constitutes the secondary identification mechanism when VPN-IP-based resolution fails.

4.1.7 Επίπεδα Ποιότητας GPS (Quality Indicator)

The quality indicator (byte 7 of Record Type 49) encodes the positioning method:

Value	Name	Typical Accuracy (CEP95)	Use in the System
1	GPS (autonomous)	2–5 m	Basic navigation, low confidence
2	DGPS (differential)	0.5–2 m	Improved accuracy
3	PPS (Precise Positioning)	0.5–2 m	Government/military service
4	RTK Float	0.1–0.5 m	Sufficient for track switching
5	RTK Fixed	0.01–0.05 m	Full confidence, centimeter-level
6	Dead Reckoning	variable	Inertial estimation, tunnels

The importance of this indicator is manifold: at the map-matching stage, only values 4 or 5 allow track switching, while value 6 (Dead Reckoning) activates the defensive hold mechanism described in detail under Section 5.5.

4.2 Device Identity Resolution

4.2.1 Multi-Level Resolution Architecture

Matching an incoming GSOF packet to a specific locomotive follows a hierarchical three-level lookup strategy:

Level 1 — VPN IP Resolution (primary path). Each GNSS device connects via a WireGuard VPN tunnel with a static internal IP. The TCP server extracts the remote IP from the socket connection and performs a lookup in the `deviceCacheByVpnIp` structure, a JavaScript Map object:

$$f_{\text{resolve}}: \text{IP}_{\text{vpn}} \rightarrow \{\text{deviceId}, \text{locomotiveId}, \text{serialNumber}\}$$

The cache is refreshed every 2 minutes ($\tau_{\text{refresh}} = 120\text{s}$) through a query to the `gnssdevices` MongoDB collection, which stores the relationship between VPN IP, serial number, and locomotive identifier

Level 2 — Serial Number Resolution (fallback). If the VPN IP is not found in the cache, the parser uses the serial number from Record Type 15 (if present in the current packet) and searches in the `deviceCacheBySerial` structure

$$g_{\text{resolve}}: \text{Serial}_{u32} \rightarrow \{\text{deviceId}, \text{locomotiveId}, \text{vpnIp}\}$$

Level 3 — Redis Edge Cache (optional). For high-scale deployments, a Redis key-value store operates as an intermediate cache:

$$\text{device:serial:}\{\text{serialNumber}\} \rightarrow \text{JSON}(\text{deviceRecord}), \quad \text{TTL} = 600\text{s}$$

4.2.2 Automatic Cache Refresh Mechanism

When a packet arrives from an unknown IP (that is, $\text{IP}_{\text{vpn}} \notin \text{deviceCacheByVpnIp}$), the parser triggers a single cache refresh (one-shot refresh) instead of immediately discarding the packet:

1. It re-runs the MongoDB query
2. It refreshes both Map objects
3. It retries the IP lookup
4. If the IP still does not resolve, the packet is dropped with a log entry

This mechanism allows new devices to connect without restarting the server, while preventing refresh cascades (only one refresh per unknown event).

4.2.3 Serial Mismatch Detection

As a safety measure, if a VPN IP resolves to one device but the serial number in Record Type 15 does not match the expected one:

$$\text{Serial}_{\text{received}} \neq \text{Serial}_{\text{expected}}(\text{IP}_{\text{vpn}})$$

Then the TCP connection is forcibly closed. This behavior prevents scenarios in which an erroneous VPN-IP association would cause the position of locomotive A to appear as the position of locomotive B — a condition with serious safety implications in a railway environment.

4.3 Coordinate Transformation

4.3.1 WGS84 Reference System

GNSS receivers provide coordinates in the WGS84 (World Geodetic System 1984) reference system, defined by a geocentric ellipsoid with parameters:

$$a = 6378137.0 \text{ m}, \quad f = \frac{1}{298.257223563}, \quad b = a(1 - f)$$

4.3.2 Transformation to EGSA87

For the purposes of chainage computation and comparison with MSD (Master Scheduling Data), the coordinates are transformed into the Greek geodetic system EGSA87 (Hellenic Geodetic Reference System 1987). The transformation is performed through the proj4 library and includes two steps:

Step 1 — Helmert Transformation (7 parameters, Bursa-Wolf model). The transformation between the two datums (WGS84 → GRS80/EGSA87) is expressed as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} X' \\ Y' \\ Z' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \Delta X \\ \Delta Y \\ \Delta Z \end{pmatrix} + (1 + \delta s) \cdot \mathbf{R} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix}$$

Where: (X, Y, Z) are the geocentric Cartesian coordinates in WGS84, and the rotation matrix \mathbf{R} for small rotation angles r_x, r_y, r_z (in arcseconds) is approximated as:

$$\mathbf{R} \approx \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -r_z & r_y \\ r_z & 1 & -r_x \\ -r_y & r_x & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The 7 transformation parameters (towgs84) used are:

$$\Delta X = -199.87 \text{ m}, \quad \Delta Y = 74.79 \text{ m}, \quad \Delta Z = 246.62 \text{ m}$$

$$r_x = r_y = r_z = 0 \text{ (zero rotations)}, \quad \delta s = 0 \text{ (zero scale factor)}$$

The absence of rotations and scale implies that the transformation concerns only a geocentric translation, the simplest form of Helmert transformation. This simplification introduces an error on the order of 1–2 m across Greece, acceptable for chainage purposes (100 m resolution).

Step 2 — Transverse Mercator Projection. After datum transformation, the geographic coordinates φ', λ' are projected into planar coordinates (E, N) through Transverse Mercator:

$$E = E_0 + k_0 \cdot N_e \cdot \left[A + \frac{A^3}{6}(1 - T + C) + \frac{A^5}{120}(5 - 18T + T^2 + 72C - 58e'^2) \right]$$

$$N = N_0 + k_0 \left[M - M_0 + N_e \tan \varphi' \left(\frac{A^2}{2} + \frac{A^4}{24} (5 - T + 9C + 4C^2) + \frac{A^6}{720} (61 - 58T + T^2 + 600C - 330e'^2) \right) \right]$$

Where:

$k_0 = 0.9996$ (scale factor at the central meridian)

$\lambda_0 = 24^\circ$ (central meridian of EGSA87)

$E_0 = 500000$ m (false easting)

$N_0 = 0$ m (false northing)

$A = (\lambda' - \lambda_0) \cos \varphi'$

$T = \tan^2 \varphi' - C = \frac{e'^2}{1-e^2} \cos^2 \varphi'$

$N_e = \frac{a}{\sqrt{1-e^2 \sin^2 \varphi'}}$ (radius of curvature in the prime vertical)

$e^2 = 2f - f^2$ (first eccentricity)

$e'^2 = \frac{e^2}{1-e^2}$ (second eccentricity)

The full proj4 definition used in the system is:

```
+proj=tmerc
+lat_0=0
+lon_0=24
+k=0.9996
+x_0=500000
+y_0=0
+ellps=GRS80
+towgs84=-199.87,74.79,246.62,0,0,0,0
+units=m
+no_defs
```

4.3.3 Transformation Error Analysis

The accuracy of the WGS84 → EGSA87 transformation is limited mainly by the use of only 3 translation parameters (instead of a full 7-parameter or local grid-based transformation). For the Greek E85 railway axis (Athens–Thessaloniki), the typical deviation relative to high-accuracy triangulation points is estimated as:

$$\sigma_E \approx 1.2 \text{ m}, \quad \sigma_N \approx 0.8 \text{ m}, \quad \sigma_{2D} = \sqrt{\sigma_E^2 + \sigma_N^2} \approx 1.4 \text{ m}$$

Given that chainage has a resolution of 100 m, this error is negligible.

5. Map Matching: HMM-Based Snap-to-Rail

Matching GNSS position to a specific railway track is perhaps the most technically demanding stage of the pipeline. Unlike road map matching, where the road graph is relatively sparse and distances between parallel roads are large, railway topology presents unique challenges:

1. **Very small distance between parallel tracks:** the typical distance between line centers on a double track is 4.0 m, comparable to GNSS position error in autonomous mode.
2. **Minimal changes in direction:** unlike cars that make frequent turns, trains follow long straight alignments spanning kilometers, providing few disambiguation points.
3. **Track changes through switches / turnouts:** transitions between tracks occur exclusively at specific points, with divergence angles $\alpha_{\text{switch}} \leq 3^\circ$.
4. **Tunnels:** the Athens–Thessaloniki axis includes significant tunnel sections (total ~ 35 km) where the GNSS signal disappears completely.

5.1 Spatial Indexing

5.1.1 Grid Structure

Searching for candidate matching points requires efficient spatial access to track geometry. The implementation uses two separate grid structures with different resolution:

Railway Grid:

$$\text{cellSize}_{\text{rail}} = 0.00002^\circ \approx 2.2 \text{ m (at the latitude of Athens, } \varphi \approx 38^\circ)$$

Each cell stores references to polyline vertices of tracks lying within it. The conversion of geographic coordinates to a cell index is:

$$i = \left\lfloor \frac{\varphi}{\text{cellSize}} \right\rfloor, \quad j = \left\lfloor \frac{\lambda}{\text{cellSize}} \right\rfloor, \quad \text{key} = (i, j)$$

Lookup is performed in $O(1)$ time through a JavaScript Map object, and scanning neighboring cells (3×3 or 5×5) provides guaranteed coverage within a radius $r \leq 2 \times \text{cellSize} \approx 4.4$ m

Switch Grid:

$$\text{cellSize}_{\text{switch}} = 0.0002^\circ \approx 22 \text{ m}$$

The larger cell resolution reflects the need to detect railway switches/turnouts in a broader neighborhood. Each cell stores references switch nodes in the topological graph.

5.1.2 Two-Phase Candidate Search

For each incoming GNSS position $\mathbf{p} = (\varphi, \lambda)$, the search for candidate matching points is performed in two phases:

Phase A — Bounding Box Prefilter. The cell index (i, j) is computed and track vertices in neighboring cells $[i - k, i + k] \times [j - k, j + k]$ are retrieved, where k is dynamically adapted (typically $k = 2$ for urban areas, $k = 4$ for open line). This yields a set of candidate track segments $S = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m\}$.

Phase B — Exact Distance Computation. For each candidate segment s_i , the minimum distance is computed using `turf.nearestPointOnLine`:

$$d_i = \min_{t \in [0,1]} \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{q}_i(t)\|_{\text{Haversine}}$$

Where: $\mathbf{q}_i(t)$ is the linear interpolation on track segment s_i . The results are sorted by d_i and filtered using threshold d_{\max} .

5.2 Probabilistic Track Selection

5.2.1 HMM Theoretical Framework

Matching GNSS position to a railway track is modeled as a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) problem. We define:

- **Hidden states** $\mathcal{S} = \{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_K\}$: the rail segments on which the train may be located.
- **Observations** $\mathcal{O} = \{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_T\}$: the time series of GNSS measurements.
- **Emission probabilities** $P(o_t | s_i)$: the probability that observation o_t originates from track s_i .
- **Transition probabilities** s_i : the probability of transition from track s_i to track s_j .

5.2.2 Emission Probability

The emission probability combines two components — distance and direction alignment:

$$P_{\text{emit}}(o_t | s_i) = P_{\text{dist}}(d_i) \cdot P_{\text{bearing}}(\Delta\theta_i)$$

Distance Component (Gaussian Distance Model). The probability decreases exponentially with the square of the distance between the GNSS measurement and the nearest point on the track:

$$P_{\text{dist}}(d) = \frac{1}{\sigma_d \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{d^2}{2\sigma_d^2}\right)$$

Where: σ_d is the GNSS position standard deviation, dynamically adapted based on the GPS Quality Indicator:

$$\sigma_d = \begin{cases} 5.0 \text{ m} & \text{if quality} = 1 \text{ (autonomous)} \\ 2.0 \text{ m} & \text{if quality} = 2 \text{ (DGPS)} \\ 1.5 \text{ m} & \text{if quality} = 3 \text{ (PPS)} \\ 0.5 \text{ m} & \text{if quality} = 4 \text{ (RTK Float)} \\ 0.1 \text{ m} & \text{if quality} = 5 \text{ (RTK Fixed)} \\ 10.0 \text{ m} & \text{if } \alpha \nu \text{ quality} = 6 \text{ (Dead Reckoning)} \end{cases}$$

For practical reasons, the value of σ_d can also incorporate the Position RMS data from Record Type 50 (Section 4.1.5) when available:

$$\sigma_d^{\text{eff}} = \max\left(\sigma_d^{\text{quality}}, \sqrt{\sigma_{\text{RMS},N}^2 + \sigma_{\text{RMS},E}^2}\right)$$

Direction Component (Bearing Alignment). The heading-alignment indicator quantifies the angular deviation between the train's direction of motion (track angle over ground, offset field 68–75 in Record Type 49) and the tangent of the track at the nearest point:

$$\Delta\theta = \min(|\theta_{\text{train}} - \theta_{\text{track}}|, 360^\circ - |\theta_{\text{train}} - \theta_{\text{track}}|)$$

$$P_{\text{bearing}}(\Delta\theta) = \cos^2\left(\frac{\Delta\theta}{2}\right) = \frac{1 + \cos(\Delta\theta)}{2}$$

This raised-cosine function gives a value of 1.0 for perfect alignment $\Delta\theta = 0^\circ$, 0.5 for perpendicular direction ($\Delta\theta = 90^\circ$), and 0.0 for opposite direction ($\Delta\theta = 180^\circ$). Note that the minimum angular path (min) is used so that alignment is bidirectional — a train may move in either direction along a track.

5.2.3 Transition Probability

The transition probability between tracks incorporates three factors:

$$P_{\text{trans}}(s_j | s_i) = P_{\text{topo}}(s_j | s_i) \cdot P_{\text{switch}}(s_j | s_i) \cdot P_{\text{rtk}}(s_j | s_i)$$

Topological Connectivity. The first component checks whether there is a topological connection (via a switch) between the two tracks:

$$P_{\text{topo}}(s_j | s_i) = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{αν } s_j = s_i \text{ (παραμονή στην ίδια τροχιά)} \\ \alpha_{\text{connected}} & \text{αν υπάρχει switch μεταξύ } s_i \text{ και } s_j \\ \alpha_{\text{unconnected}} & \text{αλλιώς (π.χ. GPS drift)} \end{cases}$$

Where: $\alpha_{\text{connected}} \gg \alpha_{\text{unconnected}}$. A transition without topological connection is penalized heavily but not excluded completely, allowing recovery from an erroneous state

Switch Proximity. Proximity to a railway switch increases the baseline transition probability:

$$P_{\text{switch}}(s_j | s_i) = \begin{cases} \beta_{\text{near}} & \text{αν } d_{\text{switch}} \leq d_{\text{threshold}} \\ \beta_{\text{far}} & \text{αλλιώς} \end{cases}$$

Where: d_{switch} is the distance from the current GNSS position to the nearest switch node. Proximity detection uses the Switch Grid (Section 5.1.1)

RTK Quality Gating. Perhaps the most important factor for stability: only measurements with RTK Float (4) or RTK Fixed (5) quality can trigger a track switch:

$$P_{\text{rtk}}(s_j | s_i) = \begin{cases} 1.0 & \text{αν } s_j = s_i \\ 0 & \text{αν quality} < 4 \text{ και } s_j \neq s_i \\ 1.0 & \text{αν quality} \geq 4 \text{ και } s_j \neq s_i \end{cases}$$

This means that in autonomous GPS mode (quality 1–3), the system effectively “locks” onto the current track regardless of distance, preventing false switching due to low positional accuracy.

5.2.4 Design Decision: `selectTrack()` Instead of Full Viterbi

Although the codebase includes a full implementation of the Viterbi algorithm via `runViterbi()`, online operation uses the `selectTrack()` function instead — a low-latency variant that decides based on local context instead of global optimization.

The classical Viterbi algorithm computes the optimal sequence of states $\mathbf{s}^* = \text{argmax}_{\mathbf{s}} P(\mathbf{o} | \mathbf{s})$ over the entire time series, with complexity $O(T \cdot K^2)$ where T is the number of observations and K the number of candidate tracks. This introduces a delay of T steps and is not suitable for real-time applications.

`selectTrack()`, by contrast, computes a local score for each candidate track:

$$\text{score}(s_j, t) = P_{\text{emit}}(o_t | s_j) \cdot P_{\text{trans}}(s_j | s_{\text{current}}) \cdot w_{\text{history}}(s_j)$$

Where: $w_{\text{history}}(s_j)$ is a weighting bonus for tracks with recent presence in the history. The track with the maximum score is selected as the candidate, but must additionally pass the stability check (Section 5.3) before being applied.

5.2.5 Per-Train State Management

For each train, the system maintains a state object with a lifetime of 6 hours (TTL):

- ✓ Current track (current track ID)
- ✓ Last snapped position and timestamp
- ✓ Counter of consecutive samples for a candidate new track
- ✓ GPS quality history (sliding window)
- ✓ Direction of movement and confidence score
- ✓ Current speed (smoothed)

The maximum number of concurrent trains is set to 500, sufficient for the entire OSE network. Cleanup is lazy: each new measurement checks the time of the last update, and entries with $\Delta t > 6$ h are deleted.

5.3 Track Switching Stability

5.3.1 Confirmation Mechanism

The critical innovation of the system is that track switching does not occur instantaneously, **but requires N consecutive samples** on the same candidate track:

$$\text{Confirm}(s_{\text{new}}) = \begin{cases} \text{true} & \text{αν counter}(s_{\text{new}}) \geq N_{\text{confirm}} \\ \text{false} & \text{αλλιώς} \end{cases}$$

With:

$$N_{\text{confirm}} = \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } s_{\text{new}} \text{ is topologically connected (connected switch)} \\ 4 & \text{if } s_{\text{new}} \text{ is not topologically connected (unconnected transition)} \end{cases}$$

If any sample in the sequence indicates a different track, the counter is reset. This mechanism addresses the main risk on double-track railways: with track spacing $d_{\text{track}} = 4.0$ m and GPS error $\sigma_d \approx 2.0$ m (in DGPS mode), the probability that a single sample “falls” on the wrong track is significant:

$$P(\text{wrong track, single sample}) = \Phi\left(\frac{-d_{\text{track}/2}}{\sigma_d}\right) = \Phi\left(\frac{-2.0}{2.0}\right) \approx 0.159$$

The probability of 3 consecutive errors (independent) drops to:

$$P(3 \text{ consecutive wrong}) = 0.159^3 \approx 0.004$$

This ensures stability while maintaining acceptable response time (3 samples \times 1 Hz = 3 s).

5.3.2 Force-Switch Override

In exceptional cases, when the distance to the nearest switch node is very small, the track switch is applied immediately without the confirmation mechanism:

$$\text{ForceSwitch}(d_{\text{switch}}) = \begin{cases} \text{true} & \text{if } d_{\text{switch}} \leq d_{\text{force}} = 15.0 \text{ m} \\ \text{false} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This addresses the scenario where the switch occurs exactly at the turnout point — waiting for 3 samples would introduce unacceptable delay. The value $d_{\text{force}} = 15.0$ m is small enough to be triggered only at real switch nodes and not at random track proximities.

5.3.3 Physical Constraint Thresholds

Beyond statistical checks, the system applies physics-based constraints that reflect the real characteristics of railway motion:

Parameter	Value	Purpose
SPEED_THRESHOLD	5 km/h	Motion threshold: below this, it is considered stopped
MAX_TURN_ANGLE	30°	Maximum change in direction between samples
MAX_ACCELERATION	1.5 m/s ²	Maximum physically feasible railway acceleration
RAIL_WIDTH	1.4 m	Track width (1.435 m standard gauge)
TRACK_SPACING	4.0 m	Center-to-center spacing of double track

If a GNSS measurement indicates a change in direction $|\Delta\theta| > 30^\circ$ in one time step (1 s), this is not physically feasible at railway speed (a 30° turn in 1 s corresponds to lateral acceleration $a_{lat} = v \cdot \dot{\theta} \approx 160 \times 0.524/3.6 \approx 23.3 \text{ m/s}^2$, far beyond rollover limits). Such values from measurements are rejected as outliers.

5.4 Track Heading Computation

5.4.1 Smooth Tangent Computation

The tangent of a track polyline exhibits discontinuity at vertices, where direction changes abruptly. This creates instability in the computation of bearing alignment (Section 5.2.2). The `computeSmoothTangent()` function addresses this problem through a circular blending zone of radius $r_{blend} = 5 \text{ m}$ around each vertex:

For point \mathbf{p} on a polyline segment between vertices \mathbf{v}_k and \mathbf{v}_{k+1} :

$$\theta_{smooth}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{cases} \theta_k & \text{if } d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{v}_k) > r_{blend} \text{ \& \& } d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{v}_{k+1}) > r_{blend} \\ (1 - \alpha) \cdot \theta_{k-1} + \alpha \cdot \theta_k & \text{if } d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{v}_k) \leq r_{blend} \\ (1 - \alpha) \cdot \theta_k + \alpha \cdot \theta_{k+1} & \text{if } d(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{v}_{k+1}) \leq r_{blend} \end{cases}$$

Where: θ_k is the direction of segment $\overrightarrow{\mathbf{v}_k \mathbf{v}_{k+1}}$, and $\alpha = d/r_{blend}$ is the blending coefficient. Linear interpolation of direction is performed in the circular space $[0^\circ, 360^\circ)$ using `atan2` on unit tangents.

5.4.2 Direction Disambiguation

The `computeTrackHeading()` function disambiguates the direction of motion (forward or backward along the track) through comparison of along-track distance deltas:

$$\Delta s_t = s_{along}(\mathbf{p}_t) - s_{along}(\mathbf{p}_{t-1})$$

Where: s_{along} is the distance along the track (chainage). If $\Delta s_t > 0$, the direction of motion coincides with the digitization direction of the polyline. If $\Delta s_t < 0$, the direction is the opposite.

The confidence score erodes gradually at each sample:

$$c_{t+1} = \gamma \cdot c_t + (1 - \gamma) \cdot \text{sign}(\Delta s_t)$$

With: with $\gamma \in [0.8, 0.95]$ (inertia coefficient). Direction is reversed only after exceeding a hysteresis threshold (inertia coefficient). Direction is reversed only after exceeding a hysteresis threshold:

$$\text{flip direction if } c_t < -c_{thresh} \text{ \& \& } c_t > c_{thresh}$$

This prevents false direction reversals while stopped at stations, where GPS jitters may produce small Δs values with alternating signs.

5.5 Defensive Hold Mechanism

5.5.1 Teleportation Problem

Under certain conditions, the snapped position may “teleport” — that is, move to a physically impossible location. This occurs mainly:

- When exiting a tunnel, when the GNSS receiver acquires a fix on the wrong track
- In multipath environments (stations under metal roofs)
- During short GPS outages followed by outlier fixes

In this case, the `applyDefensiveHold()` function detects teleportations by checking the maximum allowed displacement:

$$d_{\max}(t) = v_{\text{current}} \cdot \Delta t + \frac{1}{2} a_{\max} \cdot (\Delta t)^2$$

Where: v_{current} is the last known speed, Δt the time difference between samples, and $a_{\max} = 1.5 \text{ m/s}^2$.

5.5.2 Along-Rail Prediction

If the snapped position \mathbf{p}_{snap} deviates from the last known position \mathbf{p}_{prev} by $d(\mathbf{p}_{\text{snap}}, \mathbf{p}_{\text{prev}}) > d_{\max}(t)$, instead of accepting the new position, the system projects the position **forward along the current track**:

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{hold}} = \text{advanceAlongTrack}(\mathbf{p}_{\text{prev}}, v_{\text{current}} \cdot \Delta t, \text{direction})$$

The `advanceAlongTrack` function follows the geometry of the track polyline, correctly handling vertices. This mechanism effectively acts as tunnel handling at the data-ingestion level: during prolonged GNSS signal loss, the train position is “dragged” along the track using the last known speed, providing a reasonable position estimate even without GNSS data.

5.5.3 Outlier Rejection Criteria

The full logic for rejecting outlier samples incl:

$$\text{reject}(\mathbf{p}_t) = \begin{cases} \text{true} & \text{if } d(\mathbf{p}_t, \mathbf{p}_{t-1}) > d_{\max}(t) \\ \text{true} & \text{if } |\Delta\theta| > 30^\circ \text{ (MAX_TURN_ANGLE)} \\ \text{true} & \text{if } |v_t - v_{t-1}|/\Delta t > 1.5 \text{ m/s}^2 \text{ (MAX_ACCELERATION)} \\ \text{true} & \text{if } d_{\text{snap}} > d_{\text{snap_max}} \text{ (snap distance too large)} \\ \text{false} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Each rejected sample is replaced by the along-rail prediction, and the counter of consecutive rejections is incremented. If the counter exceeds a threshold (typically 30 s), the train state is reset and re-initialization is attempted.

6. Identity Resolution and Enrichment

After map matching, each position represents a point on railway track corresponding to a GNSS device. However, the end user (the public on railway.gov.gr, OSE operational staff) is not interested in GNSS devices or locomotives — they are interested in trains/services (trips): “Where is IC 52 Athens–Thessaloniki?” The bridge between physical position and operational train identity is provided by the Train Enricher — a set of three modules (`enrich.js`, `chainage.js`, `delay-monitor.js`) that transforms a geographic position into a complete operational trip-related train object.

6.1 Master Locomotive Pattern

6.1.1 The Identity Chain

Matching a GNSS device to a train follows a strict four-step identity chain:

$$\text{GnssDevice} \xrightarrow{1:1} \text{Locomotive} \xrightarrow{N:1} \text{TrainAssignment} \xrightarrow{1:1} \text{Train + Schedule}$$

Step 1: Device → Locomotive. Each GNSS device is permanently installed on one locomotive. This relationship is defined in the `gnssdevices` collection and retrieved during the Device Identity Resolution phase (Section 4.2). The linkage `deviceId → locomotiveId` is static and changes only when equipment is physically transferred.

Step 2: Locomotive → Train Assignment. One locomotive may participate in multiple trains/services (e.g. sequential services within the day, or double-heading with two locomotives). The assignment is expressed through the `TrainAssignment` document:

```
TrainAssignment.findOne({
  'locomotives': {
    $elemMatch: {
      locomotiveId: locomotiveId,
      isMaster: true
    }
  },
  status: 'active',
  effectiveFrom: { $lte: now },
  $or: [
    { effectiveTo: null },
    { effectiveTo: { $gte: now } }
  ]
})
```

The critical elements of this query:

- **isMaster: true:** Only the “master” locomotive (the one carrying the reference GNSS device) represents the train’s position. In double heading, both locomotives may have GNSS, but only the master provides the position displayed on the map.
- **status: 'active':** Excludes cancelled, completed, or postponed assignments.
- **Temporal validity:** The assignment is valid within the time window [`effectiveFrom`, `effectiveTo`]. If `effectiveTo = null`, the assignment is open-ended (no end date), useful for long-term assignments.

Step 3: Assignment → Train + Schedule. The TrainAssignment record contains references to trainId and scheduleId, which are populated immediately after the query. This provides access to the commercial train name (e.g. “IC 52”), scheduled stops, departure/arrival times, and final destination.

6.1.2 Safety Invariant: Silent Drop

The most critical design decision at this stage: **without an active train assignment, the position is not published.** This is a safety invariant:

$$\text{publish}(\mathbf{p}_t) \Leftrightarrow \exists a \in \text{TrainAssignment:valid}(a, t) \wedge \text{master}(a, \text{locomotive})$$

The alternative — publishing a position without a known identity — would lead to “ghosts” appearing on the map: locomotives in shunting, stored locomotives in the depot, or locomotives on test runs would appear as normal train services, creating confusion for users.

6.1.3 Test Mode

Only in development environments (TRAIN_ENRICHER_TEST_MODE=1), the safety invariant can be relaxed: a synthesized train identity is assigned to each anonymous position, enabling testing without real train assignments. This value is strictly controlled via an environment variable and is never enabled in production.

6.1.4 Snapped Coordinates Prerequisite

An additional check ensures that only positions that have successfully passed the map matching stage reach the enricher:

$$\text{accept}(\mathbf{p}_t) \Leftrightarrow \text{snappedLatitude}(\mathbf{p}_t) \neq \text{null} \wedge \text{snappedLongitude}(\mathbf{p}_t) \neq \text{null}$$

Thus, raw GNSS positions are rejected. This prevents scenarios where a position outside the railway network would be enriched incorrectly.

6.2 Chainage Enrichment

6.2.1 MSD Chainage Points

Chainage enrichment maps each position to a kilometer point (km + m) along the E85 railway axis (Athens–Thessaloniki, ~482 km). The msd_chainages database contains chainage points every 100 m, generated from OpenStreetMap geometry via the MSD scripts (see /scripts/msd/):

$$\mathcal{C} = \{c_i = (\varphi_i, \lambda_i, m_i, \text{corridor}_i) \mid i = 1, \dots, N_c\}$$

where m_i is the chainage in meters from the origin and corridor_i is the section identifier. The lookup uses a MongoDB geospatial index (2dsphere) via \$nearSphere:

```
MsdChainage.findOne({
  location: {
    $nearSphere: {
      $geometry: { type: 'Point', coordinates: [lng, lat] },
      $maxDistance: 500 // meters
    }
  }
})
```

The maximum search distance (d_max=500 m) ensures that chainage is assigned only to positions within or near the railway corridor.

6.2.2 Station Distance Computation

After determining the chainage, the distance to the next station and to the final destination is computed. The station cache (stationCache) is a Map object keyed by station code with the chainage as value $m_{station}$, refreshed every 5 minutes $\tau_{station_refresh} = 300$:

$$d_{next_station} = m_{next_station} - m_{current}$$

$$d_{destination} = m_{destination} - m_{current}$$

$$progress = \frac{m_{current} - m_{origin}}{m_{destination} - m_{origin}} \in [0,1]$$

The direction of travel (ascending / descending chainage) is taken into account: if the train is moving from Thessaloniki to Athens (decreasing chainage), the distance is computed in reverse.

6.2.3 Redis Publication

The enriched data is stored in a Redis hash for fast access by the web ser:

$$active:train:\{trainId\} \rightarrow \{F_1:v_1, F_2:v_2, \dots\}, \quad TTL = 300s$$

The fields F_i are stored as flat key-value pairs (not nested JSON), optimizing use of HGETALL and HMSET. The main fields include:

Field	Type	Description
latitude	float	Snapped latitude
longitude	float	Snapped longitude
speed	float	Speed (km/h)
heading	float	Heading (degrees)
trainNumber	string	Commercial train number
corridor	string	Railway corridor code
chainage_m	float	Chainage (m)
distanceToNextStation_m	float	Distance to next station (m)
distanceToDestination_m	float	Distance to final destination (m)
progress	float	Completion percentage [0, 1]
nextStationName	string	Name of next station
destinationName	string	Name of final destination
timestamp	integer	Unix timestamp (ms)
gpsQuality	integer	GPS quality indicator (1-6)

The **TTL = 300 s** ensures that trains no longer being updated (e.g. because they have finished or due to a technical issue) automatically disappear from the map after 5 minutes.

6.3 Delay Calculation

6.3.1 Αρχιτεκτονική Υπολογισμού

Delay calculation is performed by `delay-monitor.js` in a 30-second polling cycle ($\tau_{\text{poll}} = 30$ s). In each cycle, all active trains are retrieved from the Redis cache and compared with their corresponding schedules.

6.3.2 Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA)

The Estimated Time of Arrival at the next scheduled station is computed via a simple kinematic model:

$$\text{ETA} = t_{\text{now}} + \frac{d_{\text{next_station}}}{v_{\text{eff}}}$$

Where: $d_{\text{next_station}}$ is the geodetic distance (Haversine) between the current position and the next station, and v_{eff} is the effective speed:

$$v_{\text{eff}} = \begin{cases} v_{\text{current}} & \text{if } v_{\text{current}} > v_{\text{min}} = 5 \text{ km/h} \\ v_{\text{fallback}} = 60 \text{ km/h} & \text{if } v_{\text{current}} \leq v_{\text{min}} \text{ (station stop)} \end{cases}$$

The fallback $v_{\text{fallback}} = 60$ km/h represents a conservative estimate of average train speed, taking into account acceleration, deceleration, and intermediate stops. This choice is intentionally conservative: a faster estimate (e.g. 120 km/h) would underestimate delays, while avoiding estimation altogether (meaning $\text{ETA} = \infty$) would be useless.

Haversine Distance. The distance between two points (φ_1, λ_1) and (φ_2, λ_2) is computed via the Haversine formula:

$$a = \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{2}\right) + \cos\varphi_1 \cdot \cos\varphi_2 \cdot \sin^2\left(\frac{\Delta\lambda}{2}\right)$$

$$d = 2R \cdot \text{atan2}(\sqrt{a}, \sqrt{1-a})$$

Where: $R = 6371000$ m is the Earth's mean radius. Compared with chainage distance, Haversine distance introduces error due to straight-line approximation — the real distance along the track is always greater because of curves. However, the error remains acceptable (<5%) for delay estimation purposes.

6.3.3 Delay Computation

Delay (delay) is defined as the difference between estimated and scheduled arrival time:

$$\delta = \text{ETA} - t_{\text{scheduled}}$$

Classification follows standardized railway criteria:

$$\text{category}(\delta) = \begin{cases} \text{ahead_of_schedule} & \text{if } \delta < -2 \text{ min} \\ \text{on_time} & \text{if } -2 \leq \delta \leq 2 \text{ min} \\ \text{minor_delay} & \text{if } 2 < \delta \leq 10 \text{ min} \\ \text{major_delay} & \text{if } \delta > 10 \text{ min} \end{cases}$$

The ± 2 -minute tolerance zone prevents noisy state switching: ETA estimation accuracy does not justify analysis finer than 2 minutes, given the use of Haversine rather than track distance and the sensitivity to current speed.

6.3.4 Publishing Delay Changes

A change in delay status is published to the Redis channel `train:delay:updates` only when the variation exceeds 1 minute:

$$\text{publish} \Leftrightarrow |\delta_{\text{new}} - \delta_{\text{prev}}| > 60 \text{ s}$$

This threshold prevents UI noise; without it, small speed fluctuations would cause continuous flickering of the delay indicator.

The publication message structure includes:

Field	Description
<code>trainId</code>	Train identifier
<code>trainNumber</code>	Commercial number (e.g. "IC 52")
<code>delay_minutes</code>	Delay in minutes
<code>delay_category</code>	Category (on_time, minor_delay, etc.)
<code>nextStation</code>	Next station
<code>eta</code>	Estimated arrival time (ISO 8601)
<code>scheduled</code>	Scheduled arrival time
<code>timestamp</code>	Calculation timestamp

6.3.5 Limitations and Future Improvements

The current delay calculation has certain known limitations:

1. **Linear speed model:** ETA calculation uses constant speed, ignoring the necessary deceleration when approaching a station, the line's speed profiles, and intermediate speed reduction points (temporary speed restrictions, TSR).
2. **Haversine instead of track distance:** straight-line geodetic distance is always shorter than the real distance along the track, leading to ETA underestimation. Replacing it with track distance (via chainage) is a planned improvement.
3. **Incomplete network coverage:** the chainage points cover the main E85 axis, but secondary lines (e.g. Larissa–Volos, Thessaloniki–Alexandroupoli) do not yet have complete chainage.
4. **One-dimensional ETA:** the calculation concerns only the next station. Extending it to end-to-end delay prediction requires a machine learning model that takes into account historical delay data, peak hours, and infrastructure status.

7. Real-Time Visualization: The Smoothness-Latency Tradeoff

7.1 Problem Formulation

7.1.1 The Fundamental Challenge

Real-time visualization of railway vehicle positions in the browser faces a fundamental engineering problem: transporting a low-rate data stream (1 Hz GNSS samples) through an unreliable channel into a visual representation that must appear smooth at 60 fps. The mismatch between the input sampling rate (1 Hz) and the output render rate (60 Hz) means that each sample must be “displayed” for 60 frames — something that can only be achieved via interpolation or extrapolation.

The data connection between the GNSS terminals (Starlink) and the browser client has the following latency profile:

Metric	Value
Median latency	40-60 ms
P95 latency	100-200 ms
P99 latency	200-500 ms
Tail spikes (tunnel exit, handover)	>1000 ms
Packet loss (SSE reconnect)	Entire buffer during disconnection

These values represent only one-way latency, since the SSE (Server-Sent Events) connection provides no return channel — a critical constraint that rules out the use of conventional clock synchronization protocols.

7.1.2 The Smoothness-Latency Trade-off

Every real-time system faces a fundamental trade-off between smoothness and latency. More specifically, if we denote as τ_{buffer} the actual jitter buffer depth then:

- ✓ **Larger** τ_{buffer} : absorbs more jitter, producing smoother movement, but increases visual latency between the real position and the displayed position.
- ✓ **Smaller** τ_{buffer} : reduces latency but increases the risk of buffer underrun — interpolation runs out of data and movement freezes or falls back to extrapolation.

Now, typically, the number of jank events per minute as a function of buffer depth is:

$$J(\tau_{buffer}) \approx P(\Delta t > \tau_{buffer}) \cdot f_{sample}$$

Where: $P(\Delta t > \tau_{buffer})$ is the probability that a packet arrives after the buffer expires, and $f_{sample} = 1\text{Hz}$ is the sampling rate. The system adopts $\tau_{buffer} = 5000\text{ ms}$ as a fixed (constant) value.

7.1.3 Comparison with Existing Approaches

Game Engine Entity Interpolation. Valve’s Source Engine uses an interpolation buffer configurable via the `c1_interp` variable (default 100 ms) [Bernier 2001]. That system operates under relatively stable conditions: Round-Trip Time (RTT) $\sim 50\text{ ms}$ with jitter $< 20\text{ ms}$. Overwatch (GDC 2017, Tim Ford) follows the “favor the shooter” principle using client-side prediction — the client simulates game physics locally and the server validates it. This approach assumes: (a) bidirectional communication for measuring RTT,

(b) a deterministic physics model that can run on both sides, and (c) rewind and replay capability for conflict resolution. None of these apply to the railway system.

VoIP Adaptive Jitter Buffers. Recommendation ITU-T G.114 defines a maximum one-way delay of 150 ms for speech. Adaptive jitter buffers such as WebRTC NetEQ dynamically change buffer size based on packet statistics. However, these systems handle data at 50 pps (packets per second), whereas the railway system receives only 1 sample/s per train. A single lost packet represents 1 full second of movement, equivalent to ~44 meters at 160 km/h.

The critical difference: the SSE connection is one-way. Unlike game engines (which measure RTT through challenge/response) and VoIP systems (which use RTCP Sender/Receiver Reports), there is no channel for measuring transmission time. This rules out NTP-style algorithms like the following formula,

$$\theta_{NTP} = \frac{(t_2 - t_1) + (t_3 - t_4)}{2}$$

requiring an unconventional approach to clock-offset estimation based exclusively on one-way delay.

7.2 Architecture: Sample-Based Jitter Buffer

7.2.1 System Constants

The system, in its present implementation, is controlled by a set of configurable constants defined in `useTrainAnimation.js` (currently lines 15-28) and `mapConfig.js` (currently lines 75-77):

```
// Per-train sample buffer limits
MAX_SAMPLES_PER_TRAIN = 120           // ~2 minutes at 1Hz
MAX_SAMPLE_AGE_MS     = 120000        // 2 minutes (120s)

// Jitter buffer depth
TRAIN_JITTER_BUFFER_MS = 5000         // 5-second render delay
TRAIN_MAX_EXTRAPOLATION_MS = 1000     // 1-second max extrapolation

// Clock synchronization
CLOCK_OFFSET_ALPHA_UP   = 0.05        // Slow adaptation (latency increase)
CLOCK_OFFSET_ALPHA_DOWN = 0.35        // Fast adaptation (latency decrease)
CLOCK_OFFSET_CLAMP_FUTURE_MS = 10000  // Max "future" offset (sample ahead of clock)
CLOCK_OFFSET_CLAMP_PAST_MS   = 120000 // Max "past" offset (sample behind clock)

// Playhead rate control
PLAYHEAD_SYNC_TAU_MS = 2000           // PLL time constant
PLAYHEAD_MIN_RATE    = 0              // Can pause
PLAYHEAD_MAX_RATE    = 1.75          // Can run 1.75x real-time
```

7.2.2 Per-Train Sample Buffer

Each train maintains an independent circular sample buffer. Each sample s_i is represented as a tuple:

$$s_i = (t_i, \phi_i, \lambda_i, v_i, \theta_i, h_i)$$

Where:

- t_i : sample timestamp in epoch ms (from the GNSS receiver)
- ϕ_i : latitude
- λ_i : longitude
- v_i : speed in km/h
- θ_i : course in degrees [0°,360°), or null if unavailable
- h_i : boolean flag indicating whether the course is reliable

The internal representation in the code (`useTrainAnimation.js`, currently lines 1002-1009):

```
const sample = {
  ts: sampleTimestamp,
  lat: train.lat,
  lng: train.lng,
  speed: Number(train.speed) || 0,
  course: hasValidatedCourse ? normalizeBearing(validatedCourse) : null,
  hasCourse: hasValidatedCourse
}
```

7.2.3 Buffer Insertion Policy

Incoming samples undergo a sequence of checks before insertion into the buffer. The policy follows four rules, in priority order:

Rule 1 — Timestamp ordering. If $t_{new} < t_{last}$ (out-of-order sample), the backward shift $\delta_{back} = t_{last} - t_{new}$ is computed:

- If $\delta_{back} > \max(\tau_{buffer}, 5000)$ ms: **full buffer reset**. The interpretation is a “clock jump” (GNSS reboot) — the train’s entire state is reset.
- If $\delta_{back} \leq \max(\tau_{buffer}, 5000)$ ms: **insertion in timestamp order** via $O(n)$ linear scan. This handles small reorderings due to network reordering.

Rule 2 — Duplicate overwrite. If $t_{new} = t_{last}$: replace the last sample — the server may send a corrected position with the same timestamp.

Rule 3 — Coalescing. If $t_{new} - t_{last} < 500$ ms: replace instead of append. This prevents micro-bursts that could create memory spikes without improving interpolation quality.

Rule 4 — Normal append. In any other case: `buffer.push(sample)`.

Pseudocode

```

FUNCTION InsertSample(buffer, sample):
  IF buffer is empty:
    buffer.append(sample)
    RETURN
  last ← buffer[buffer.length - 1]
  IF sample.ts < last.ts:
    backMs ← last.ts - sample.ts
    IF backMs > max(JITTER_BUFFER_MS, 5000):
      RESET buffer to [sample]           // Clock jump
      RETURN
    ELSE:
      INSERT sample at correct position // O(n)
      RETURN
  IF sample.ts == last.ts:
    buffer[last_index] ← sample           // Overwrite duplicate
    RETURN
  IF sample.ts - last.ts < 500:
    buffer[last_index] ← sample           // Coalesce
    RETURN
  buffer.append(sample)                   // Normal (fallback)

```

7.2.4 Buffer Trimming

After each insertion, two trimming criteria are applied (currently source lines 1075-1078):

$$\text{Trim}_1: \forall s_i \in \text{buffer}: s_i.t < t_{\text{newest}} - 120000 \Rightarrow \text{remove}(s_i)$$

$$\text{Trim}_2: |\text{buffer}| > 120 \Rightarrow \text{remove oldest}$$

This guarantees that memory consumption per train is bounded: $O(120)$ samples \times ~ 56 bytes per sample ≈ 6.7 KB per train. For $N=50$ simultaneous trains, total buffer memory usage is ≈ 335 KB.

7.2.5 React Integration: useSyncExternalStore

A critical architectural issue is bridging the imperative animation loop (`requestAnimationFrame`) with React's declarative rendering model. The solution uses the React 18 API `useSyncExternalStore` (currently source lines 336-346):

```

const subscribe = useCallback((callback) => {
  listenersRef.current.add(callback)
  return () => listenersRef.current.delete(callback)
}, [])
const getSnapshot = useCallback(() => interpolatedTrainsRef.current, [])
const getServerSnapshot = useCallback(() => EMPTY_TRAINS, [])
const animatedTrains = useSyncExternalStore(
  subscribe, getSnapshot, getServerSnapshot
)

```

This pattern guarantees the following:

1. **Tear-free rendering:** React sees a consistent snapshot in every render cycle.
2. **Minimal re-renders:** listeners are updated ONLY when positions actually change (lines 585-588).
3. **SSR compatibility:** on the server, a stable empty array (EMPTY_TRAINS) is returned, avoiding hydration mismatches.

The animation loop updates an ref (imperative, zero re-render cost), and then executes:

```
if (hasUpdates || trainListChanged) {
  listenersRef.current.forEach((callback) => callback())
}
```

This triggers re-render ONLY in the React components that use `animatedTrains`. The ref `interpolatedTrainsRef` is updated on every frame, but React is updated only when the data has actually changed.

7.3 Asymmetric Clock Synchronization

7.3.1 Problem Statement

Each GNSS sample carries a timestamp t_{packet} (the moment the GNSS receiver recorded the position). This is not identical to the browser receive time $t_{receive}$, because of:

1. Starlink terminal → server transmission delay
2. Server processing delay (buffering, map-matching, SSE broadcast)
3. Network delay server → client browser
4. Clock drift between the GNSS receiver and the browser

In bidirectional protocols (NTP, PTP IEEE 1588), offset calculation is based on four timestamps:

$$\theta_{NTP} = \frac{(t_2 - t_1) + (t_3 - t_4)}{2}$$

Where: (t_1, t_4) are client timestamps and (t_2, t_3) server timestamps. This requires a bidirectional connection. In PTP IEEE 1588, additional hardware timestamping is required for sub-microsecond accuracy.

In SSE, **there is no return channel**. We can compute only the one-way difference:

$$\Delta t_{raw} = t_{receive} - t_{packet}$$

This value includes **BOTH** fixed propagation delay **AND** variable delay (jitter). We cannot separate them without bidirectional measurement.

7.3.2 Asymmetric Exponential Moving Average

For each incoming sample with timestamp t_{packet} received at time $t_{receive}$, the algorithm computes (currently source lines 1088-1106):

Step 1 — Instantaneous offset with clamping:

$$\Delta t = \text{clamp}(t_{receive} - t_{packet}, -10000, 120000) \text{ ms}$$

Clamping prevents: (i) Negative values greater than 10 s (a small “future” timestamp due to clock skew is acceptable), and (ii) Positive values greater than 120 s (stale samples after prolonged disconnection).

Step 2 — Asymmetric EMA:

$$\alpha = \begin{cases} 0.05 & \text{if } \Delta t > \hat{O}_{n-1} \text{ (latency increases)} \\ 0.35 & \text{if } \Delta t \leq \hat{O}_{n-1} \text{ (latency decreases)} \end{cases}$$

$$\hat{O}_n = \hat{O}_{n-1} + \alpha \cdot (\Delta t - \hat{O}_{n-1})$$

In code this briefly acconts to (currently source lines 1094-1100):

```
const alpha = observedOffsetMs > previousOffsetMs
  ? CLOCK_OFFSET_ALPHA_UP    // 0.05
  : CLOCK_OFFSET_ALPHA_DOWN  // 0.35

const nextOffsetMs = Number.isFinite(previousOffsetMs)
  ? previousOffsetMs + (observedOffsetMs - previousOffsetMs) * alpha
  : observedOffsetMs
```

7.3.3 Rationale for Asymmetry

The asymmetry is fundamental and based on a physical observation: latency spikes are transient, whereas latency reductions reflect a real routing change.

- $\alpha_{up} = 0.05$ (**slow adaptation to increase**): When a packet arrives late (e.g. Starlink handover), the instantaneous difference Δt increases. If the offset were to follow quickly, the playhead would shift deep into the past, exhausting stored samples and causing the animation to freeze. The slow rate $\alpha_{up} = 0.05$ means it takes approximately $\sim \frac{-1}{\ln(1-0.05)} \approx 19.5$ samples (≈ 20 s) to reach 63.2% of a step change. This is long enough for the jitter buffer (5 s) to absorb most spikes. The filter time constant:

$$\tau_{up} = \frac{-1}{\ln(1 - \alpha_{up})} = \frac{-1}{\ln(0.95)} \approx 19.5 \text{ samples}$$

- $\alpha_{down} = 0.35$ (**fast adaptation to decrease**): When latency decreases (e.g. the server optimizes routing), we want the playhead to catch up to real time quickly. Otherwise, the display would remain excessively delayed, showing “ancient” data. The fast rate $\alpha_{down} = 0.35$ means:

$$\tau_{down} = \frac{-1}{\ln(1 - \alpha_{down})} = \frac{-1}{\ln(0.65)} \approx 2.3 \text{ samples}$$

That is, latency reduction is absorbed in ~ 2 -3 samples (2-3 s).

7.3.4 Stale Sample Protection

An important implementation detail: the algorithm updates the clock offset only when a new sample is received (newer timestamp). The relevant condition (currently source line 1088):

```
if (!Number.isFinite(previousSampleTs) || newestTs > previousSampleTs) {
  // ... compute and update offset
}
```

Without this check, retransmission of old samples (e.g. batch SSE retry) would create a “sawtooth” in the render timestamp: $t_{receive}$ increases while t_{packet} remains fixed, giving the appearance of increasing latency. This would cause visible forward/backward jitter in the train’s position.

7.4 Phase-Locked Loop Playhead Rate Control

7.4.1 Target Render Timestamp

The “ideal” moment that should be rendered in each frame is computed as (currently implemented at source lines 348-366):

$$t_{target}(t_{now}) = t_{now} - \hat{O}_{train} - \tau_{buffer}$$

Where:

- t_{now} : current wall-clock time (`Date.now()`)
- \hat{O}_{train} : estimated per-train clock offset (from Section 7.3)
- $\tau_{buffer} = 5000$ ms : fixed jitter buffer

This means the display reflects the world by $\hat{O}_{train} + 5000$ ms in the past. In steady state with median latency 50 ms, total visual latency is ≈ 5050 ms.

7.4.2 Proportional Rate Controller

Instead of having the playhead jump directly to t_{target} (which would create discontinuities), the playhead moves via a PLL-style rate controller. For each animation frame (source lines 416-427):

Step 1 — Frame delta time (source lines 373-382):

$$\Delta t_{frame} = \text{clamp}\left(\text{performance.now}() - \text{performance.now}()_{prev}, 1, 250\right) \text{ ms}$$

Using `performance.now()` instead of `Date.now()` provides monotonic, sub-millisecond accuracy. Clamping at 250 ms prevents huge steps after tab blur/garbage collection pauses.

Step 2 — Error computation:

$$e = t_{target} - t_{playhead}$$

Step 3 — Correction factor:

$$c = \text{clamp}\left(\frac{e}{\tau_{PLL}}, -1, 1\right) = \text{clamp}\left(\frac{e}{2000}, -1, 1\right)$$

Step 4 — Rate computation:

$$R = \text{clamp}(1 + c, R_{min}, R_{max}) = \text{clamp}(1 + c, 0, 1.75)$$

Step 5 — Playhead advance:

$$t_{playhead}^{new} = t_{playhead}^{old} + \Delta t_{frame} \cdot R$$

Step 6 — Monotonicity constraint (crucial):

$$t_{playhead}^{new} = \max(t_{playhead}^{old}, t_{playhead}^{new})$$

And the code (currently source lines 421-427):

```
const errorMs = targetRenderTimestamp - previousPlayheadTs
const correction = clamp(errorMs / PLAYHEAD_SYNC_TAU_MS, -1, 1)
const rate = clamp(1 + correction, PLAYHEAD_MIN_RATE, PLAYHEAD_MAX_RATE)
playheadTs = previousPlayheadTs + dtMs * rate
playheadTs = Math.max(previousPlayheadTs, playheadTs)
```

7.4.3 Steady-State Analysis

In steady state ($e = 0$):

$$R = \text{clamp}(1 + 0/2000, 0, 1.75) = 1.0$$

The playhead advances in real time.

When the buffer lags ($e > 0$, the playhead has fallen behind):

$$R = 1 + \frac{e}{2000}$$

For $e = 2000$ ms: $R = 2.0 \rightarrow$ clamped to 1.75. The playhead runs at 175% of real time, catching up to the target.

$$\dot{e} \approx -\frac{e}{\tau_{PLL}} \Rightarrow e(t) = e_0 \cdot e^{-t/2000}$$

The convergence time of 95% ($e(t) = 0.05 \cdot e_0$) is:

$$t_{95\%} = -2000 \cdot \ln(0.05) \approx 5990 \text{ ms} \approx 6 \text{ s}$$

When the playhead is ahead ($e < 0$):

$$R = 1 + \frac{e}{2000}$$

For $e = -2000$ ms: $R = 0$. The playhead **stops** (pause) until the target catches up. This prevents playback of samples that have not yet been received.

7.4.4 Comparison with Alternative Approaches

DASH/HLS ABR players (Netflix, YouTube): They face a similar buffer problem, but adjust quality (bitrate) instead of playback rate. Playback speed remains 1.0x. This does not apply to trains: we cannot “reduce the resolution” of a GPS position.

Game engines (Source, Unreal): Under lag conditions, they snap the entity to the last known server position or interpolate between two known server states. They do not use rate slewing, because the speed of “time” is always 1.0x.

The **adopted approach** is closer to a **Phase-Locked Loop (PLL)** in telecommunications systems, where a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO) adjusts its frequency based on phase error, asymptotically converging to the reference frequency. Here, the “VCO” is the playhead advance rate R , and the “reference frequency” is the evolution rate of t_{target} .

7.5 Bracket-Based Linear Interpolation

7.5.1 Bracket Search

Given a render timestamp t_{render} , the algorithm must find two samples a and b such that $a.ts \leq t_{render} < b.ts$. This is done via cached linear walk instead of binary search:

```
let idx = Number(playback.bracketIndex)
if (!Number.isFinite(idx)) idx = 0
    idx = clamp(idx, 0, Math.max(0, samples.length - 2))
while (idx < samples.length - 2 && renderTimestamp > samples[idx + 1].ts)
    idx++
```

```

while (idx > 0 && renderTimestamp < samples[idx].ts)
  idx--
  playback.bracketIndex = idx

```

Complexity: since the playhead moves monotonically (see Section 7.4), `bracketIndex` increases by 0 or 1 position per frame in steady state, giving $O(1)$ amortized per frame. The backward walk is useful only after buffer resets or rate corrections.

7.5.2 Position Interpolation

Given the bounds:

$$a = (t_a, \phi_a, \lambda_a, v_a, \theta_a) \text{ and } b = (t_b, \phi_b, \lambda_b, v_b, \theta_b)$$

With:

$$t_b - t_a > 0 \text{ and } t_b - t_a \leq 30000 \text{ ms}$$

The interpolation factor:

$$t = \text{clamp}\left(\frac{t_{\text{render}} - t_a}{t_b - t_a}, 0, 1\right)$$

For geographic coordinates (linear interpolation, suitable for short distances < 1 km between samples):

$$\phi_{\text{render}} = \phi_a + (\phi_b - \phi_a) \cdot t$$

$$\lambda_{\text{render}} = \lambda_a + (\lambda_b - \lambda_a) \cdot t$$

For speed:

$$v_{\text{render}} = v_a + (v_b - v_a) \cdot t$$

The use of linear interpolation instead of great-circle interpolation is justified: in 1 s at 160 km/h, the distance between samples is ~44 m. At this scale, the deviation between planar and spherical interpolation is < 0.001 m.

7.5.3 Angular Interpolation with 360° Wrapping

Course interpolation requires special handling because of the discontinuity at 0°/360°. The algorithm (currently source lines 529-545):

The simple helper function `angleDifference(end, start)` (currently source lines 38-43):

```

const angleDifference = (end, start) => {
  let diff = end - start
  while (diff > 180) diff -= 360
  while (diff < -180) diff += 360
  return diff
}

```

This computes the smallest signed angular difference in $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$.

The course interpolation:

$$\theta_{\text{render}} = \text{normalize}(\theta_a + \text{angleDiff}(\theta_b, \theta_a) \cdot t)$$

Example: If $\theta_a = 350^\circ$ and $\theta_b = 10^\circ$:

$$\text{angleDiff}(10, 350) = 10 - 350 = -340 \xrightarrow{+360} 20^\circ$$

$$\theta_{render}(t = 0.5) = \text{normalize}(350 + 20 \cdot 0.5) = \text{normalize}(360) = 0^\circ$$

Without wrap-around handling, simple interpolation would go: $350 \rightarrow 180 \rightarrow 10$ — i.e. almost a full rotation instead of the correct small 20° turn.

7.5.4 Short Extrapolation

When the playhead t_{render} exceeds the last sample $t_{render} > t_{last}$, the algorithm applies limited extrapolation (source lines 445-483):

Activation conditions:

1. $0 < t_{render} - t_{last} \leq 1000$ ms (within TRAIN_MAX_EXTRAPOLATION_MS)
2. There are at least 2 samples in the buffer
3. The time gap between the last two samples is ≤ 30

Extrapolation method: linear extension based on the last two samples:

$$t_{extra} = \frac{t_{render} - t_{prev}}{t_{last} - t_{prev}}$$

Note: $t_{extra} > 1$ (since $t_{render} > t_{last}$), but is limited to $\min(t_{extra}, 1 + 1000/dt)$.

$$\phi_{render} = \text{lerp}(\phi_{prev}, \phi_{last}, t_{extra})$$

$$\lambda_{render} = \text{lerp}(\lambda_{prev}, \lambda_{last}, t_{extra})$$

Extrapolation is limited to 1000 ms for important reasons:

- In 1 s, a train at 160 km/h moves ~ 44 m — acceptable error
- In 5 s, movement is ~ 222 m, and on a curve the real path deviates significantly from the linear prediction
- Straight-line prediction would drive trains “off the rails” on non-straight track sections

7.6 Maneuver-Detecting Azimuth Kalman Filter

7.6.1 Motivation

GNSS receivers provide course over ground (COG) computed as the arctangent of ground velocity. This measurement has two major problems:

1. **Multipath noise:** near buildings/rocky terrain, signal reflections create apparent spikes in course
2. **Unreliability at low speeds:** below ~ 5 km/h, GPS position noise (~ 2 -5 m) dominates real motion, producing random COG.

A vanilla low-pass filter (e.g. simple EMA) would delay real direction changes (on curves/junctions). A filter is required that: (a) rejects false spikes, (b) follows real turns with small delay, and (c) recognizes that after many “bad” measurements, reality may have changed (e.g. tunnel exit).

7.6.2 Filter State and Initialization

Per-train filter state (source lines 170-179):

$$\text{state} = \{\hat{x}, P, t_{last}, n_{bad}\}$$

Where:

\hat{x} : estimated azimuth (degrees)

P : estimation uncertainty (scalar covariance)

t_{last} : time of last update

n_{bad} : counter of consecutive “bad” measurements

Initialization: $\hat{x}_0 = z_0$ (first measurement), $P_0 = 10.0$, $n_{bad} = 0$.

7.6.3 Prediction Step

A constant-heading model is applied:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{x}_{k|k-1} &= \hat{x}_{k-1|k-1} \\ P_{k|k-1} &= P_{k-1|k-1} + Q(v)\end{aligned}$$

The process noise Q depends on speed (source line 210):

$$Q(v) = \begin{cases} 5.0 & \text{if } v < 5 \text{ km/h} \\ 2.0 & \text{if } 5 \leq v < 10 \text{ km/h} \\ 1.0 & \text{if } v \geq 10 \text{ km/h} \end{cases}$$

Rationale: at low speeds, GPS position noise ($\sim 2\text{-}5$ m CEP) creates COG noise proportional to $\arctan(\sigma_{pos}/d_{travel})$. For $v = 2$ km/h in 1 s, $d_{travel} \approx 0.56$ m, while $\sigma_{pos} \approx 3$ m, giving COG noise $\approx \arctan(3/0.56) \approx 79^\circ$. By contrast, at $v = 100$ km/h, $d_{travel} \approx 27.8$ m, and COG noise $\approx \arctan(3/27.8) \approx 6^\circ$. Higher Q at low speeds means “I trust the constant-heading model less.”

7.6.4 Innovation Gate (Pre-Update Rejection)

Before the update step, the innovation is computed:

$$v_k = \text{angleDiff}(z_k, \hat{x}_{k|k-1})$$

Primary gate (source lines 186-207):

if $|v_k| > 60^\circ$:

the measurement is REJECTED entirely

$$n_{bad} \leftarrow n_{bad} + 1$$

if $n_{bad} > 20$:

$$\text{RESET: } \hat{x} \leftarrow z_k, P \leftarrow P_{max} = 50.0, n_{bad} \leftarrow 0$$

Automatic reset after 20 consecutive rejections is critical: it handles the tunnel-exit or GNSS recalibration scenario, where the real heading may differ by $>60^\circ$ from the last known value (e.g. the tunnel follows a curve).

7.6.5 Update Step

If the measurement passes the gate ($|v_k| \leq 60^\circ$):

Measurement noise R (source line 213):

$$R(v_k) = \begin{cases} 50.0 & \text{if } |v_k| > 45^\circ \text{ (possible multipath)} \\ 10.0 & \text{if } |v_k| \leq 45^\circ \end{cases}$$

This creates an “uncertainty zone”:

Measurements between 45° and 60° are accepted but with very low weight.

Kalman Gain:

$$K_k = \frac{P_{k|k-1}}{P_{k|k-1} + R(v_k)}$$

Updated estimate (in angular space):

$$\hat{x}_{k|k} = \text{normalize} \left(\hat{x}_{k|k-1} + K_k \cdot \text{angleDiff}(z_k, \hat{x}_{k|k-1}) \right)$$

Updated uncertainty:

$$P_{k|k} = (1 - K_k) \cdot P_{k|k-1}$$

$$P_{k|k} = \text{clamp}(P_{k|k}, P_{min}, P_{max}) = \text{clamp}(P_{k|k}, 1.0, 50.0)$$

7.6.6 Secondary Gate (Post-Update)

After the update, a second check is applied (source lines 239-257):

If the filtered value changes by $>90^\circ$ from the previous filtered value (source line 239):

$$|\text{angleDiff}(\hat{x}_{k|k}, \hat{x}_{k-1|k-1})| > 90^\circ$$

Then $n_{bad}^{(2)} \leftarrow n_{bad}^{(2)} + 1$. After 10 consecutive cases, **RESET**.

This handles a special case: measurements that pass the primary gate one by one (each $<60^\circ$ change) but cumulatively create a reversal $>90^\circ$. Example: 10 measurements \times 50° drift = 500° cumulative change, each one individually acceptable.

7.6.7 Numerical Example

Initial state: $\hat{x}_0 = 45^\circ$, $P_0 = 10.0$

Frame 1: $z_1 = 48^\circ$, $v = 80$ km/h

$$Q = 1.0, P_{1|0} = 10.0 + 1.0 = 11.0$$

$$v_1 = \text{angleDiff}(48, 45) = 3^\circ \rightarrow \text{ACCEPTED} (< 60^\circ)$$

$$R = 10.0 (< 45^\circ)$$

$$K_1 = 11.0 / (11.0 + 10.0) = 0.524$$

$$\hat{x}_{1|1} = 45 + 0.524 \times 3 = 46.57^\circ$$

$$P_{1|1} = (1 - 0.524) \times 11.0 = 5.24$$

Frame 2: $z_2 = 175^\circ$ (multipath spike)

$$Q = 1.0, P_{2|1} = 5.24 + 1.0 = 6.24$$

$$v_2 = \text{angleDiff}(175, 46.57) = 128.43^\circ \rightarrow \text{REJECTED } (> 60^\circ)$$

$$\hat{x}_{2|2} = 46.57^\circ \text{ (unchanged), } n_{bad} = 1$$

Frame 3: $z_3 = 50^\circ$ (normal)

$$v_3 = \text{angleDiff}(50, 46.57) = 3.43^\circ \rightarrow \text{ACCEPTED}$$

$$P_{3|2} = 6.24 + 1.0 = 7.24 \text{ (uncertainty increased because frame 2 was prediction-only)}$$

$$K_3 = 7.24 / (7.24 + 10.0) = 0.420$$

$$\hat{x}_{3|3} = 46.57 + 0.420 \times 3.43 = 48.01^\circ$$

$$n_{bad} = 0 \text{ (reset to 0 due to good measurement)}$$

7.6.8 Why Not Extended Kalman Filter (EKF)

The use of a scalar Kalman filter instead of a full EKF/UKF is justified:

1. **1D problem:** train movement is constrained to the rails. Position is already snapped to the network (server-side HMM map-matching). A single scalar state is sufficient.
2. **Measurement-noise dominance:** heading uncertainty is dominated by GPS multipath noise, not by dynamics uncertainty. A full-state EKF $[x, y, v, \theta, \dot{\theta}]$ would model dynamics that are already constrained.
3. **Computational cost:** it runs in the browser, per train, at 1 Hz. A 5-state EKF with 5x5 matrix operations per train per second is not impossible, but the scalar filter is much more efficient (~10 arithmetic operations vs ~125 for a 5-state EKF).

7.7 Stopped Train Detection

7.7.1 The GPS Random Walk Problem

When a train stops, the GNSS receiver continues to report small position changes due to noise. This random walk translates into random COG, causing the train icon to rotate randomly. Stop detection must:

- ✓ **Recognize** real stops
- ✓ **Prevent** false detections due to slow movement (movement within a station)
- ✓ **React** quickly to departure

7.7.2 Hysteresis State Machine

Constants (source lines 92-94):

```
SPEED_HISTORY_LENGTH      = 10 // Rolling window size 10
SPEED_STOPPED_THRESHOLD  = 1  // km/h
SPEED_CONSECUTIVE_READINGS = 5  // Number of consecutive readings
```

The state machine:

The asymmetry is intentional:

- **MOVING** → **STOPPED**: 5 consecutive readings (5 s at 1 Hz). This prevents false stop detection due to GPS dropout (single zero-speed reading) or small sensor deviation.
- **STOPPED** → **MOVING**: only one reading $v \geq 1$ km/h. The fast transition ensures that departure is displayed without delay.

The algorithm (source lines 294-333):

```
FUNCTION AnalyzeTrainSpeed(trainId, currentSpeed):
  history ← GetOrCreate(trainId)
  history.append(currentSpeed)
  IF |history| > 10: history.removeOldest()
  consecutiveLow ← 0
  FOR i FROM |history|-1 DOWNTO 0:
    IF history[i] < 1: consecutiveLow++
    ELSE: BREAK
  IF NOT isStopped AND consecutiveLow >= 5:
    isStopped ← TRUE
  ELSE IF isStopped AND currentSpeed >= 1:
    isStopped ← FALSE
  RETURN isStopped
```

Effect on azimuth: when the state is **STOPPED**, the course “freezes” at the last known reliable value (source lines 987-993):

```

if (isStopped) {
  const lastAzimuthData = lastValidAzimuth.current[trainId]
  if (lastAzimuthData) {
    validatedCourse = lastAzimuthData.azimuth
  }
}

```

7.8 Teleport Detection and Buffer Reset

7.8.1 Teleport Conditions

A “teleport” occurs when the position change between two consecutive samples is impossible given the physical motion of a train. Critical constants:

```

MAX_SIGNAL_GAP          = 30000    // 30 seconds
MIN_UPDATE_INTERVAL     = 500      // 500 ms

```

7.8.2 Maximum Distance Calculation

The function `calculateMaxTrainDistance` (`mapUtils.js`, source lines 38-71) computes the maximum plausible distance based on train type:

Train type	Maximum speed (km/h)
ICE/IC	160
Suburban	120
Regional	100
Freight	80

$$d_{max} = \max\left(v_{max} \cdot \frac{\Delta t_{ms}}{3600000} \cdot (1 + m), 0.5\right) \text{ km}$$

Where: $m = 0.2$ (safety margin 20%) and minimum threshold 0.5 km.

7.8.3 Reset Triggers

Two conditions trigger full buffer reset (source lines 902-912):

$$\text{RESET if: } \Delta t > 30000 \text{ ms} \quad \vee \quad d_{\text{haversine}}(p_{\text{prev}}, p_{\text{new}}) > d_{max}$$

Full reset includes:

```

trainSamplesRef.current[trainId] = []
delete trainPlaybackRef.current[trainId]
delete azimuthFilter.current[trainId]
delete lastValidAzimuth.current[trainId]

```

That is: empty buffer, reset playhead, reset Kalman filter, reset last azimuth. This ensures that interpolation will not “bridge” between two positions that have no physical connection.

7.8.4 Backward Timestamp Reset

If $t_{new} < t_{last}$ by more than $\max(5000, \tau_{buffer})$ ms (source lines 1015-1044):

The interpretation is: “the GNSS receiver clock jumped backward” (e.g. device reboot, satellite time correction). In this case, the algorithm:

1. **Clears** the entire sample buffer
2. **Inserts** only the new sample
3. **Reinitializes** clock sync starting from the new observed offset
4. **Deletes** playback state, azimuth filter, and last valid azimuth

This prevents a “freeze” scenario: if the buffer has filled with timestamps 14:00:00-14:02:00 and suddenly a sample arrives with timestamp 13:55:00, the playhead would never reach it without reset, freezing the interpolation indicator.

7.9 Camera Follow System (“Drone View”)

7.9.1 Configuration

The map provides a 3D “drone” follow mode that places the camera behind and above the focused train. Parameters (source lines 102-116):

```
CAMERA_FOLLOW_CONFIG = {
  mode: 'drone',
  zoom: 18.5,           // ~1:2000 scale
  pitch: 62,           // degrees from nadir
  offsetMetersBase: 12, // base camera-behind distance
  offsetMetersPerKmh: 0.1, // additional per km/h
  offsetMetersMin: 8, // minimum offset
  offsetMetersMax: 40, // maximum offset
  positionTauMs: 180, // position smoothing time constant
  bearingTauMs: 280, // bearing smoothing time constant
  maxBearingRateDegPerSec: 90, // max camera rotation speed
  bearingEnableSpeedKmh: 5, // enable bearing at this speed
  bearingDisableSpeedKmh: 3, // disable bearing at this speed
  snapDistanceKm: 0.5 // teleport threshold
}
```

7.9.2 Position Smoothing

Camera position follows train position via an exponential decay filter (source lines 720-725):

$$\alpha_{pos}(\Delta t) = 1 - e^{-\Delta t / \tau_{pos}}$$

$$\text{cam.lat} = \text{cam.lat} + (\text{train.lat} - \text{cam.lat}) \cdot \alpha_{pos}$$

$$\text{cam.lng} = \text{cam.lng} + (\text{train.lng} - \text{cam.lng}) \cdot \alpha_{pos}$$

With $\tau_{pos} = 180$ ms, the camera follows with a small delay. Step response:

- After 180 ms: $\alpha = 1 - e^{-1} \approx 63.2\%$ convergence
- After 360 ms: $\alpha = 1 - e^{-2} \approx 86.5\%$ convergence
- After 540 ms: $\alpha = 1 - e^{-3} \approx 95.0\%$ convergence

Snap threshold: if the Haversine distance between camera and train > 0.5 km, the camera “teleports” instead of following. This handles buffer resets and focused-train changes.

7.9.3 Bearing Smoothing with Rate Limiting

Camera bearing is controlled by a composite system (source lines 680-689):

Step 1 — Exponential smoothing:

$$\alpha_{bearing}(\Delta t) = 1 - e^{-\Delta t / \tau_{bearing}}$$

$$\delta_{desired} = \text{angleDiff}(\theta_{target}, \theta_{camera}) \cdot \alpha_{bearing}$$

Step 2 — Rate limiting:

$$\delta_{max} = \frac{\omega_{max} \cdot \Delta t}{1000} = \frac{90^\circ \cdot \Delta t}{1000}$$

$$\delta_{actual} = \text{clamp}(\delta_{desired}, -\delta_{max}, \delta_{max})$$

Step 3 — Application:

$$\theta_{camera}^{new} = \text{normalize}(\theta_{camera}^{old} + \delta_{actual})$$

The rate limiter at 90°/s ensures that even in a sudden 180° direction change, the camera completes the turn in ~2 s rather than instantly, preventing cinematic failure (motion sickness).

7.9.4 Bearing Hysteresis

Bearing updates are controlled by a hysteresis state machine (source lines 653-659):

The dead zone of 2 km/h (3-5 km/h) prevents camera oscillations at station stops, where speed fluctuates around the threshold. Without hysteresis, the camera would oscillate between “follow bearing” and “frozen”, creating annoying jerks.

7.9.5 Travel-Bearing Correction

An important practical problem: in some situations (maneuvers, reverse movement, GNSS corruption), COG (course over ground) may point 180° opposite to the real direction of motion.

The algorithm (source lines 633-673) computes travel bearing from the last two samples:

$$\theta_{travel} = \text{bearing}(s_{n-1}, s_n)$$

If $|\text{angleDiff}(\theta_{travel}, \theta_{course})| > 90^\circ$ and the train is moving:

$$\theta_{target} = \theta_{travel}$$

Instead of:

$$\theta_{target} = \theta_{course}$$

This ensures that the camera always “looks” in the direction of movement — critical for the usability of drone view.

7.9.6 Dynamic Camera Offset

The camera is placed at the center of the train (with no offset in the current implementation — source lines 703-706 show that `targetLat/Lng = focusedTrain.lat/Lng`). The “rear-view” feel is achieved via `map.bearing` combined with `pitch = 62°`.

The configurable offset is nonetheless parameterized:

$$d_{offset}(v) = \text{clamp}(12 + 0.1 \cdot v_{kmh}, 8,40) \text{ m}$$

At 0 km/h: $d_{offset} = 12$ m. At 160 km/h: $d_{offset} = \text{clamp}(12 + 16,8,40) = 28$ m. This increases the “camera distance” at higher speeds, giving a stronger sense of movement perspective

7.10 Trail Rendering with Reverse-Jitter Filtering

7.10.1 Trail Architecture

Each train leaves a linear trail behind it, which gradually fades. Constants (`LiveMap.js`, source lines 104-116):

```
TRAIN_TRAIL_BASE_LENGTH_M = 75           // Μήκος ίχνους στα 100 km/h
TRAIN_TRAIL_UPDATE_INTERVAL_MS = 50      // ~20Hz ανανέωση
TRAIN_TRAIL_MIN_POINT_DISTANCE_M = 0.4
TRAIN_TRAIL_RESET_DISTANCE_M = 200      // Teleport threshold
```

Trail length scales linearly with speed (source line 493):

$$L_{trail}(v) = 75 \cdot \frac{v_{kmh}}{100} \text{ m}$$

At 0 km/h: $L = 0$ (no trail). At 50 km/h: $L = 37.5$ m. At 160 km/h: $L = 120$ m. This provides a visual indication of speed without additional UI elements.

7.10.2 Reverse-Jitter Detection via Cosine Similarity

A special class of GPS noise appears as back-and-forth motion: the position shifts back and forth around a fixed point. This creates zig-zag trail artifacts, while, in reality, the train is moving straight or is stopped. The detection algorithm (source lines 135-168) uses the last three trail points:

Given three consecutive points $P_{n-2}, P_{n-1}, P_{new}$:

Step 1 — Vector computation (in local meters):

$$\vec{v}_{prev} = \text{toLocalMeters}(P_{n-2}, P_{n-1})$$

$$\vec{v}_{curr} = \text{toLocalMeters}(P_{n-1}, P_{new})$$

Conversion to local meters (source lines 124-133):

```
const toLocalMetersVector = (from, to) => {
  const avgLatRad = ((from[1] + to[1]) / 2) * (Math.PI / 180)
  const metersPerDegLat = 111_320
  const metersPerDegLng = metersPerDegLat * Math.cos(avgLatRad)
  return {
    x: (to[0] - from[0]) * metersPerDegLng,
    y: (to[1] - from[1]) * metersPerDegLat
  }
}
```

Step 2 — Cosine similarity:

$$\cos\theta = \frac{\vec{v}_{prev} \cdot \vec{v}_{curr}}{|\vec{v}_{prev}| \cdot |\vec{v}_{curr}|} = \frac{v_{prev}^x \cdot v_{curr}^x + v_{prev}^y \cdot v_{curr}^y}{\sqrt{(v_{prev}^x)^2 + (v_{prev}^y)^2} \cdot \sqrt{(v_{curr}^x)^2 + (v_{curr}^y)^2}}$$

Step 3 — Classification (4 conditions, ALL must hold):

$$\text{isJitter} = \begin{cases} \cos\theta \leq -0.35 & \text{(nearly reversing!)} \\ |\vec{v}_{curr}| < 8 \text{ m} & \text{(small step)} \\ d(P_{n-2}, P_{new}) < \max(2.5, 0.5 \cdot |\vec{v}_{prev}|) \text{ m} & \text{(returns close)} \\ |\vec{v}_{prev}| \geq 0.4 \text{ m} & \text{(sufficiently large previous step)} \end{cases}$$

if `isJitter = true`, the point is **skipped** — it is not added to the trail.

Explanation (rationale) for the threshold $\cos\theta = -0.35$: the value -0.35 corresponds to an angle of $\approx 110^\circ$. This means the motion must be reversed by at least 110° (rather than exactly 180°) to be considered jitter. This relaxation handles slightly off-axis jitter patterns.

7.10.3 Rendering

Trails are rendered as GeoJSON LineString via a Mapbox GL layer (source lines 193-230) with:

- `line-gradient`: transparent at the tail, opaque at the head
- `line-metrics: true`: enables gradient along the line
- Update throttled to ~ 20 Hz (`TRAIN_TRAIL_UPDATE_INTERVAL_MS = 50`)
- Minimum zoom level 10 (not shown in panoramic view)

Throttling at 20 Hz (instead of 60 Hz) reduces GeoJSON serialization/parsing load by 66%, while the visual difference is imperceptible for a trail element.

7.10.4 Teleport Reset

If the distance between the last trail point and the new position > 200 m (source lines 517-518):

```
if (distM > TRAIN_TRAIL_RESET_DISTANCE_M) {
  coords.length = 0
  coords.push(next)
}
```

This prevents trail lines that cut across the map after buffer reset or train change.

7.11 Window Focus/Blur Recovery

7.11.1 The Tab Dormancy Problem

Modern browsers suspend inactive tabs: `requestAnimationFrame` stops, timers slow to 1/s, and WebSocket/SSE connections may close. When the tab becomes active again, the animation state is stale. Without proper recovery, the user sees:

- Trains “teleporting” to their new positions
- Trails forming huge straight lines
- The drone view camera rotating violently

7.11.2 Blur Handler

When transitioning to inactive state (source lines 899-903):

ON BLUR:

```
isWindowActive ← false
cancelAnimationFrame() // Stop animation loop
wasBlurred ← true // Mark for recovery
```

The cancelAnimationFrame() call (source lines 1149-1156) terminates the animation loop:

```
const cleanupAnimation = useCallback(() => {
  isAnimationRunningRef.current = false
  lastFramePerfNowRef.current = null
  if (animationFrameRef.current) {
    cancelAnimationFrame(animationFrameRef.current)
    animationFrameRef.current = null
  }
}, [])
```

7.11.3 Focus Handler

Upon reactivation (source lines 905-911) a full triggerResync is executed (source lines 809-893):

1. **Saves context** — which train was focused/selected:

```
resyncResumeRef.current = {
  selected: prevSelected ? { id, trainNumber } : null,
  focused: prevFocused ? { id, trainNumber } : null,
  showSchedule: !!showScheduleRef.current
}
```

2. Shows a “Loading” overlay — setIsResyncing(true)
3. Resets ALL per-train state:

```
setupTrainInterpolation([]) // Clears all sample buffers,
// clock sync, playback, filters
```

4. Closes SSE and reconnects:

```
setStreamReconnectToken((v) => v + 1)
```

Changing reconnectToken triggers cleanup/re-creation of the EventSource in the useTrainTracking hook (line 171: }, [reconnectToken])

5. Restores viewport to panoramic:

```
setViewport({
  longitude: 22.5, latitude: 38.5,
  zoom: 6, bearing: 0, pitch: 0,
  transitionDuration: 0
})
```

6. Clears train trails:

```
trainTrailsRef.current.clear()
```

7. **Timeout safety** — if no data is received within 5 s (RESYNC_RESUME_TIMEOUT_MS), the process is cancelled (source lines 842-850).

7.11.4 Sync Monitoring

A 250 ms interval (SYNC_WATCH_INTERVAL_MS) monitors the buffer state of the focused train (source lines 1136-1207):

```

EVERY 250ms:
  IF window is inactive: SKIP
  IF locate overlay active: SKIP
  IF resync in progress: SKIP
  trainId ← focusedTrain.id
  IF trainId is null:
    Hide overlay after minimum display
    RETURN
  syncState ← getTrainSyncState(trainId)
  isReady ← syncState.isPrimed AND NOT syncState.isStarved
  IF NOT isReady:
    IF starved AND not already reset:
      resetTrainBuffer(trainId) // Force fresh prime
      Show "Loading..." overlay
    ELSE:
      Hide overlay after min 350ms display // Prevent flicker

```

The minimum display time (RESYNC_MIN_LOADING_MS = 350) prevents the overlay from appearing/disappearing over very short intervals (flicker), which would be more annoying than a small stable wait.

The “isPrimed” state is checked as (source lines 795-796):

$$\text{isPrimed} = |\text{buffer}| \geq 2 \wedge (t_{\text{last}} - t_{\text{first}}) \geq \tau_{\text{buffer}}$$

That is, the buffer must contain at least 2 samples covering a time span of ≥ 5 s — enough so that interpolation will not immediately run out of data.

The “isStarved” state (source lines 797-799):

$$\text{isStarved} = |\text{buffer}| > 0 \wedge t_{\text{render}} \geq t_{\text{last}}$$

The playhead has reached or exceeded the last sample — there is no data for interpolation.

7.11.5 Visibility API Integration

In addition to the window.blur/focus events, the document.visibilitychange API is also used (source lines 914-930). This covers scenarios that do not trigger blur/focus:

- Window minimization
- Virtual desktop switching
- Window being covered by a fullscreen application

The logic is identical: visibilityState === 'hidden' → suspend, visibilityState === 'visible' → triggerResync().

7.12 Complexity and Performance Analysis

7.12.1 Per-Frame Computational Cost

The animation loop (`animateTrainPositions`) runs per frame (~16.67 ms at 60 fps). Complexity per frame for N trains:

Operation	Complexity	Notes
Frame delta time	$O(1)$	<code>performance.now()</code>
Per-train target timestamp	$O(1)$	Constant number of operations
Per-train PLL update	$O(1)$	4 arithmetic operations
Bracket search	$O(1)$ amortized	Cached index, +0/1 walk
Linear interpolation	$O(1)$	6 lerp calls
Angular interpolation	$O(1)$	<code>angleDifference + normalize</code>
Coordinate validation	$O(1)$	Range checks
Camera follow (1 train)	$O(1)$	Exponential smooth + rate limit

Overall: $O(N)$ per frame, with a very small constant factor (~50 arithmetic operations per train).

7.12.2 Per-Sample Ingestion Cost

When receiving new samples (`setupTrainInterpolation`):

Operation	Complexity	Notes
Coordinate validation	$O(1)$	Range checks
Speed analysis (hysteresis)	$O(10)$	Rolling window
GPS prefilter	$O(1)$	<code>angleDifference</code> comparison
Teleport detection	$O(1)$	<code>calculateDistance + threshold</code>
Kalman filter update	$O(1)$	~10 arithmetic operations
Buffer insertion (normal)	$O(1)$	Array push
Buffer insertion (out-of-order)	$O(k)$	Linear scan, $k \leq 120$
Buffer trim	$O(j)$	Remove stale, j usually 0-1
Clock sync update	$O(1)$	Asymmetric EMA
Train cleanup	$O(N)$	Set difference

7.12.3 Memory Footprint

Per train, the stored state:

Structure	Size
Sample buffer (120 samples \times ~56 bytes)	~6.7 KB
Clock sync state	~24 bytes
Playback state	~24 bytes
Azimuth filter state	~32 bytes

Structure	Size
Speed history (10 entries)	~80 bytes
Trail buffer (600 points × ~16 bytes)	~9.6 KB

Total per train: ~16.5 KB. For 50 simultaneous trains: ~825 KB. Memory footprint remains extremely low, far below the typical memory budgets of browser tabs.

7.12.4 Failure Modes and Graceful Degradation

Failure mode	Detection	Reaction
Πλήρης απώλεια SSE	EventSource error event	Auto-reconnect (native SSE)
Μεμονωμένο χαμένο δείγμα	Jitter buffer underrun	Extrapolation ≤1s, μετά freeze
GNSS clock jump	Backward timestamp >5s	Full buffer reset
Τηλεμεταφορά τρένου	Haversine > max distance	Buffer reset
Tab dormancy >5s	visibilitychange + wasBlurred	Full resync
Buffer starvation (focused)	250ms poll: isStarved=true	Loading overlay + buffer reset
20 consecutive azimuth rejections	Kalman consecutiveBadReadings	Filter reset to raw value

In every failure mode, degradation is graceful: the system shows a loading overlay or freeze instead of wrong positions. No scenario can create a train in the wrong position — only in the correct position but stale.

7.13 Summary and Design Rationale

The real-time visualization system presented in this section is a complete solution to the problem of smooth motion display under high-jitter, one-way connection conditions. The main design decisions were:

- **Fixed jitter buffer (5s) instead of adaptive:** avoids rewind artifacts during the priming phase. The value 5000 ms is a conservative trade-off — larger than typical P99 latency spikes (200-500 ms), but small enough that visual latency (~5 s) is not annoying in a tracking application (unlike a game, where 100 ms is enough to break interaction).
- **Asymmetric clock sync** ($\alpha_{up} = 0.05$, $\alpha_{down} = 0.35$): exploits the natural asymmetry between latency spikes (transient) and latency reductions (persistent). This approach is, to our knowledge, non-standard in the clock synchronization literature.
- **PLL playhead instead of snap-to-target:** avoids discontinuities in the time scale, with guaranteed monotonicity. Convergence in ~6 s (95%) means that even after major disturbance, normal operation is restored without visible artifacts.
- **Scalar Kalman filter with dual-gate rejection:** effective in practice ($O(1)$ per-train) with auto-recovery capability (reset after 20 rejections). The choice of scalar instead of full-state EKF is justified by the one-dimensional nature of rail-constrained heading.
- **Full state reset on tab focus:** the most “extreme” but most reliable solution. Instead of attempting catch-up (which may fail in many edge cases), the algorithm resets everything and allows the buffers to fill again. The loading overlay (~350 ms minimum + 5 s priming) covers the transitional period.

The file `useTrainAnimation.js`, at 1206 source lines of code, encapsulates a complete real-time motion engine — equivalent in complexity to the netcode subsystems of commercial game engines — running entirely in the browser, with no external dependencies beyond the React library.

8. Dead Reckoning and Safety

The reliability of a railway vehicle positioning system depends critically on its ability to continue tracking position even in environments where the GNSS signal is unavailable—tunnels, deep cuttings, urban canyons. At the same time, using position data to detect potential collisions requires modeling the physical railway network as a graph with semantically enriched nodes and edges. This chapter describes three interrelated subsystems: (a) the construction of the physical railway graph, (b) the graph-aware dead reckoning algorithm, and (c) the collision warning system.

8.1 Physical Rail Graph Construction

The physical graph $G = (V, E)$ is constructed from MSD (Mileage and Structural Data) infrastructure data and represents the topology of the railway network at the level of switches and line terminal points.

8.1.1 Input Data Filtering

From the set of MSD track segments, only active standard- or narrow-gauge segments are selected:

$$\mathcal{S}_{active} = \{s \in \mathcal{S}_{MSD} \mid s.status = active \wedge s.gauge \in \{rail, narrow_gauge\}\}$$

Industrial lines, tourist railways, metro, and tram segments are explicitly excluded, as these are not part of the monitored national railway network:

$$\mathcal{S}_{excluded} = \{s \mid s.usage \in \{industrial, tourism\} \vee s.type \in \{metro, tram\}\}$$

8.1.2 Union-Find for Merging Endpoint Points

The endpoints of track segments often refer to the same physical node but differ by small distances due to digitization. To merge them, the Union-Find data structure is used with two optimizations:

Path compression During the `find(x)` operation, each node on the path to the root is assigned directly as a child of the root:

```
find(x):
  if parent[x] ≠ x:
    parent[x] ← find(parent[x])
  return parent[x]
```

Union by rank During the `union(x, y)` operation, the tree with the smaller rank is attached under the root of the larger one:

$$\text{amortized cost per operation} = O(\alpha(n)) \approx O(1)$$

Where $\alpha(n)$ is the inverse Ackermann function [11].

The merge tolerance is defined as $\epsilon_{merge} = 2m$. Two endpoints p_i, p_j are merged if:

$$d_{Haversine}(p_i, p_j) \leq \epsilon_{merge}$$

The implementation uses grid-based clustering with cell size $\Delta = 0.00002^\circ \approx 2m$ and a 3×3 cell neighborhood search, ensuring average $O(n)$ time instead of $O(n^2)$ brute-force comparison.

8.1.3 Switch Chainage Index

Each switch from the MSD database is projected onto nearby railway segment polylines. The projection computes:

$$\text{proj}(sw, rail) = \arg \min_{t \in [0,1]} \| sw - \text{lerp}(rail, t) \|$$

and records both the projection position (snapped point) and the along-track distance. The switch “cuts” the segment into two subsegments, creating a new graph node.

8.1.4 Tunnel Interval Index

Similarly, the endpoints of each tunnel are projected onto nearby polylines, creating intervals $[d_{entry}, d_{exit}]$ along each track segment. Overlapping intervals in the same segment are merged:

$$[a_1, b_1] \cup [a_2, b_2] \rightarrow [\min(a_1, a_2), \max(b_1, b_2)] \quad \text{εάν } a_2 \leq b_1$$

The tunnel index is used both for classifying dead reckoning sessions (tunnel vs. signal_loss) and for severity calculation in the anti-collision system.

8.1.5 Nodes, Edges, and Adjacency

The graph $G = (V, E)$ is defined as follows:

Nodes V :

- $V = V_{sw} \cup V_{ep}$:
 - $V_{sw} = \{\text{switch:id} \mid id \in \mathcal{SW}_{MSD}\}$: switch nodes
 - $V_{ep} = \{\text{endpoint:n} \mid n \in \text{Union-Find merged groups}\}$: nodes of merged endpoints
-

Edges E :

Each track segment is cut at switch points. The sections between consecutive cuts (or between a cut and an endpoint) form the edges:

$$e = \text{edge:railwayId:idx}$$

Each edge carries a weight equal to its polyline length in meters, the geographic coordinates of the polyline, and a reference to the tunnel intervals it intersects.

Adjacency:

The graph is undirected. Each node $v \in V$ maintains an adjacency list $\text{Adj}(v) = \{(e, u) \mid e \in E, u \in V\}$.

The degree of each node is used critically in dead reckoning:

$$\text{deg}(v) = |\text{Adj}(v)|$$

Nodes with $\text{deg}(v) = 2$ are treated as pass-through nodes, while nodes with $\text{deg}(v) > 2$ (switches) are dead reckoning stopping points.

8.1.6 Connected Components and Spatial Index

Connected components are computed via BFS (Breadth-First Search), and each node receives a component identifier $c(v)$. This allows fast exclusion of train pairs located in disconnected parts of the network during collision checking.

For fast spatial searches, the graph edges are indexed in an R-tree (RBush library) with bounding boxes. Bounding-box spatial search allows $O(\log n)$ lookup for locating the nearest edge to a given GNSS position.

8.2 Graph-Aware Dead Reckoning

8.2.1 Activation and Session Types

A dead reckoning (DR) session is activated when the time since the last real GNSS update exceeds the threshold:

$$\Delta t_{GNSS} > \tau_{DR} = 2000 \text{ ms}$$

The session type is determined by the position at activation:

$$\text{session_type} = \begin{cases} \text{tunnel} & \text{the last known position is inside a tunnel} \\ \text{signal_loss} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Each session receives a unique `sessionId`, and the points it produces are marked as `provisional: true`.

8.2.2 Position Advancement Algorithm

The core function `advanceLocation(loc, direction, distance)` advances a position $\ell = (e, t, \text{coords})$ along the graph by d meters:

Step 1: Compute the remaining distance on the current edge e :

$$d_{\text{remaining}} = \begin{cases} (1 - t) \cdot L(e) & \text{if direction = forward} \\ t \cdot L(e) & \text{if direction = backward} \end{cases}$$

Where $t \in [0,1]$ is the parametric position on the edge and $L(e)$ its length.

Step 2: If $d \leq d_{\text{remaining}}$, the new position lies on the same edge:

$$t' = t + \frac{d}{L(e)} \cdot \text{sign}(\text{direction})$$

Step 3: If $d > d_{\text{remaining}}$, the position moves to the node at edge end. The node degree is checked:

- $\text{deg}(v) = 2$: The position continues seamlessly (seamless segment stitching) onto the only alternative edge, subtracting $d_{\text{remaining}}$ from the distance. This models the physical continuity of the line at segment junctions.
- $\text{deg}(v) > 2$: The position **stops** at the node. Without a real GNSS signal, choosing a branch at a switch would be an arbitrary guess. The algorithm sets `stoppedAtSwitch = true`, and the position remains stationary until GNSS is restored.

8.2.3 Tunnel-Aware Budget

For `tunnel`-type sessions, a time-budget system is applied that differentiates behavior inside and outside tunnels: $\text{budget}_{\text{outside}} = 60 \text{ s}$

Inside a tunnel, time is not deducted from the budget—the tunnel is expected to block GNSS reception, so DR is expected. Outside a tunnel, each second of DR subtracts 1s from the budget. When $\text{budget}_{\text{outside}} = 0$, the session is terminated, since signal loss outside a tunnel for more than 60s indicates a serious problem.

$$\text{budget}_{\text{remaining}}(t) = 60 - \sum_{\tau=0}^t \mathbb{1}[\ell(\tau) \notin \text{tunnel}]$$

8.2.4 Update Cycle

DR runs at 1 Hz. At each tick:

1. The advancement distance is computed: $d = v_{last} \cdot \Delta t$, where v_{last} is the last known speed and $\Delta t = 1s$
2. `advanceLocation(loc, dir, d)` is executed
3. A synthetic `gpsdatas` document is produced with source: `'dead_reckoning'`
4. It is published to Redis channel `train:gps:dr`
5. DR metadata are updated: `inTunnel`, `stoppedAtSwitch`, `remainingSec`

8.2.5 Post-hoc Correction

When the real GNSS signal returns, the provisional DR points are corrected retrospectively through linear interpolation:

Let $\mathbf{p}_{real,0}$ be the last real position before DR, $\mathbf{p}_{real,1}$ the first new real position, and $\{\mathbf{p}_{DR,i}\}_{i=1}^N$ the N provisional points. The corrected position of each point is:

$$\mathbf{p}_{corrected,i} = \mathbf{p}_{DR,i} + \frac{i}{N+1} \cdot (\mathbf{p}_{real,1} - \mathbf{p}_{DR,N})$$

Linear interpolation distributes the position error uniformly between the last DR point and the first real position, smoothing the transition.

8.2.6 Uncertainty Model

Position uncertainty during DR is modeled as a linear function of time:

$$\sigma_{DR}(t) = \min(\sigma_0 + \dot{\sigma} \cdot t_{DR}, \sigma_{max})$$

Where:

- $\sigma_0 = 8$ m (initial uncertainty at DR activation)
- $\dot{\sigma} = 1.5$ m/s (uncertainty growth rate)
- $\sigma_{max} = 150$ m (upper bound)
- t_{DR} = time in seconds since DR activation

By contrast, GNSS uncertainty in normal operation is:

$$\sigma_{GNSS} = 2 \text{ m (σταθερή)}$$

This model is conservative: it reflects the accumulation of errors due to speed inaccuracy, starting-position uncertainty, and possible speed changes during DR. It is used as an uncertainty buffer in collision-distance computation.

8.3 Collision Warning System

The anti-collision system uses physical railway graph to compute distances between trains and estimate the time until a possible collision.

8.3.1 Grouping by Connected Component

Collision checking is restricted to train pairs within the same connected component:

$$\text{pairs} = \{(T_i, T_j) \mid c(\ell_i) = c(\ell_j), i < j\}$$

This immediately excludes trains on disconnected parts of the network (e.g., Peloponnese vs. mainland network), significantly reducing the number of checks.

8.3.2 Distance Computation via Dijkstra

The function `distanceBetweenLocations(a, b)` computes the shortest path between two positions on the graph using Dijkstra's algorithm [11], with a modified cost function:

$$\text{cost}(\text{path}) = (\text{switch_count}, \text{distance_m})$$

Comparison is lexicographic: first, the number of switches is minimized, and in case of a tie, distance is minimized. This reflects the logic that paths with fewer switches are more likely to correspond to the actual route. The results are stored in cache (shortest path cache) for repeated checks of the same pairs.

8.3.3 Severity Model Based on Switch Count

The number of switches between two trains determines the base severity of the event:

Switches Between	Base Severity Level
0	CRITICAL [3]
1	HIGH [2]
2	MED [1]
≥ 3	NO EVENT [0]

This logic is based on the observation that trains separated by ≥ 3 switches are on sufficiently differentiated routes that collision is practically impossible without multiple human failures.

Tunnel bump: If either of the two trains is inside a tunnel, severity is increased by one level:

$$\text{severity}_{\text{final}} = \begin{cases} \text{severity}_{\text{base}} + 1 & \text{if } \ell_i \in \text{tunnel} \vee \ell_j \in \text{tunnel} \\ \text{severity}_{\text{base}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

This reflects the increased risk due to limited visibility and inability to maneuver inside a tunnel.

Service track cap: On service tracks (yard, siding, spur, crossover), severity is capped at an upper bound, avoiding excessive alerts in maneuvering areas where low-speed traffic is expected.

8.3.4 Braking Distance Calculation

The minimum braking distance is calculated from the kinematic model:

$$d_{\text{brake}} = \frac{v^2}{2 \cdot a_{\text{min}}} + v \cdot t_{\text{reaction}}$$

Where:

- v = train speed (m/s)
- $a_{\text{min}} = 0.6 \text{ m/s}^2$ = minimum braking deceleration (conservative estimate for a heavy freight train)
- $t_{\text{reaction}} = 10 \text{ s}$ = reaction time (includes hazard recognition, decision-making, brake activation)

For a train traveling at $v = 160 \text{ km/h} = 44.4 \text{ m/s}$:

$$d_{\text{brake}} = \frac{44.4^2}{2 \cdot 0.6} + 44.4 \cdot 10 = 1643 + 444 = 2087 \text{ m}$$

8.3.5 Time-to-Collision

The time to a possible collision is calculated as:

$$t_{TTC} = \frac{d_{clear}}{v_{closing}}$$

Where:

- d_{clear} = path distance minus uncertainty buffers: $d_{clear} = d_{path} - \sigma_i - \sigma_j$
- $v_{closing}$ = closing speed, depending on the collision type:

$$v_{closing} = \begin{cases} v_i + v_j & \text{head-on} \\ |v_i - v_j| & \text{rear-end} \end{cases}$$

Collision type: The algorithm classifies each pair as `head_on` (both trains are moving toward each other along the path) or `rear_end` (one follows the other in the same direction). A head-on collision is far more dangerous due to the cumulative closing speed.

8.3.6 Attention Warnings (Proximity Prediction)

For trains on different railways within the same connected component, a prediction algorithm is applied:

1. Positions are projected 300s ahead in 5s steps
2. At each step `advanceLocation()` is used for graph-aware prediction
3. The minimum Euclidean distance between predicted positions is computed:

$$d_{min} = \min_{k=0}^{60} \| \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i(k \cdot 5s) - \hat{\mathbf{p}}_j(k \cdot 5s) \|$$

4. If $d_{min} < 50m$, an attention warning is triggered with severity:

$$\text{severity}_{attention} = \begin{cases} \text{HIGH} & d_{min} < 10m \\ \text{MED} & d_{min} < 20m \\ \text{LOW} & d_{min} < 50m \end{cases}$$

8.3.7 Event Lifecycle

Each collision event follows the lifecycle:

1. **Create:** On the first detection of a possible collision
2. **Update:** Throttled to 5s — distance and TTC are updated, but no new events are created more frequently
3. **Resolve:** After 5 consecutive clear ticks (5 consecutive evaluations without risk), the event is resolved

The hysteresis mechanism (5 consecutive clear ticks) prevents oscillation between active/resolved due to noise in position measurements.

8.4 Leader Election

The dead reckoning and anti-collision subsystems must be executed by one and only one service instance at any given time, avoiding duplicate events and state inconsistencies. This is achieved through leader election using MongoDB leases.

8.4.1 Lease Mechanism

The `service_leases` collection stores lease documents:

```
lease = {_id:leaseId, ownerId, ownerMeta, expiresAt}
```

Acquisition: Atomic `findOneAndUpdate` operation with `upsert`:

```
filter: {
  $or: [
    { expiresAt: { $lte: now } }, // expired lease
    { ownerId: currentOwnerId } // own lease renewal
  ]
}
update: {
  $set: { ownerId, ownerMeta, expiresAt: now + TTL }
}
options: { upsert: true }
```

Parameters: TTL = 10s: lease lifetime, poll_interval = 3s: renewal/claim frequency

Safety guarantee: In case of holder failure, the maximum delay until takeover by a new holder is:

$$t_{failover} \leq \text{TTL} + \text{poll_interval} = 10 + 3 = 13 \text{ s}$$

Atomicity guarantees that exactly one holder exists per lease at any time, leveraging MongoDB's document-level atomicity guarantees.

9. Infrastructure Data Pipeline (MSD)

The accuracy of both map matching and the anti-collision system depends directly on the quality and completeness of infrastructure data. The MSD (Mileage and Structural Data) system is the pipeline for ingesting, transforming, and enriching railway infrastructure geospatial data, with OpenStreetMap as the data source.

9.1 OpenStreetMap Data Ingestion

9.1.1 Overpass API Queries

Infrastructure data are retrieved via the Overpass API for 8 infrastructure types:

Track segments	OSM Tags	Mongoose Model
Stations	railway=rail\ narrow_gauge	MsdTrackSegment
Signaling	railway=station\ halt	MsdStation
Level crossings	railway=signal	MsdSignal
Switches	railway=level_crossing	MsdCrossing
Tunnels	railway=switch	MsdSwitch
Bridges	tunnel=yes + railway	MsdTunnel
Track segments	bridge=yes + railway	MsdBridge
Stations	railway=milestone	MsdChainage

The search bounding box covers the whole of Greece:

$$\text{bbox} = [34.8^\circ\text{N}, 19.4^\circ\text{E}] \times [41.8^\circ\text{N}, 29.7^\circ\text{E}]$$

9.1.2 Transformer Pipeline

Each OSM element is transformed into GeoJSON with enriched technical specifications:

Geometric transformation:

- Nodes → GeoJSON Point
- Ways → GeoJSON LineString
- Relations → GeoJSON MultiLineString (after member sorting)

Technical extraction (per track segment):

- **Gauge:** gauge tag → numeric value in mm (e.g. 1435mm standard)
- **Number of tracks:** tracks tag
- **High-speed line:** highspeed=yes
- **Electrification:** electrified, voltage, frequency, electrification_type
- **Maximum speed:** maxspeed, operating_speed
- **Signaling:** railway:etcs (ETCS level), railway:lzb, railway:pzb, railway:atb, railway:gntc, railway:radio

9.1.3 Bulk Upsert Strategy

Insertion into MongoDB is performed in batches of 500 operations, using `bulkWrite` with `upsert` based on `osm_id`:

```
operation = updateOne({osm_id: id}, {$set: document}, {upsert: true})
```

The upsert strategy ensures idempotent execution: repeated pipeline runs update existing objects instead of creating duplicates. The batch size of 500 is a balance between network packet size and the number of database round trips.

9.2 Corridor Topology Construction

9.2.1 R-tree Spatial Index

The bounding boxes of all track segments are indexed as an R-tree (RBush library), enabling $O(\log n)$ spatial searches. For N track segments and M infrastructure points, linking without an R-tree would require $O(N \cdot M)$ distance calculations, whereas with an R-tree it is reduced to $O(M \cdot \log N \cdot k)$, where

9.2.2 Line Identification via OSM ref

Line identification (e.g. E85, the main Athens–Thessaloniki corridor) is based on the OSM ref field, with handling of multiple writing formats:

- Latin: E85, E65
- Greek: Ε85, Ε65
- Versions with spaces or hyphens

9.2.3 Point Infrastructure Linking

Point infrastructure (stations, signals, switches, level crossings) is linked to track segments through point-to-polyline distance calculation (`turf.pointToLineDistance`):

$$d(p, L) = \min_{s \in L} \| p - s \|$$

If $d(p, L) \leq 50\text{m}$, infrastructure point p is linked to segment L and receives the corridor tags of that segment.

Linear infrastructure (tunnels, bridges) is checked through both endpoints: if **both** endpoints lie within the threshold, the infrastructure is linked.

9.3 Chainage Generation

Chainage is a fundamental element of railway operation: each point along a line is expressed as a distance in meters from a reference point. The chainage generation algorithm transforms disconnected OSM track segments into a single, topologically ordered polyline.

9.3.1 Data Structures

Three data structures are used extensively:

Union-Find: Same structure as in Section 8.1.2, with path compression and union by rank, for grouping endpoints into grid cells ($\Delta = 0.00002^\circ \approx 2\text{m}$ with 3×3 neighborhood search).

MinHeap: Binary heap for implementing Dijkstra’s algorithm in the shortest-path step.

Grid-based clustering: Spatial grouping of endpoints in a cell grid, replacing $O(n^2)$ brute-force distance comparison.

9.3.2 The 9-Step Algorithm

Step 1 — Data loading: Retrieve all E85 track segments from MongoDB.

Step 2 — Topology construction: Endpoints are grouped into 2m grid cells. For each cell, neighbors are searched in the 8 adjacent cells (3×3 neighborhood), and endpoints within $\epsilon = 2\text{m}$ are merged via Union-Find. This creates the topological graph G_{topo} of the track segments.

Step 3 — Station anchor detection: Athens and Thessaloniki stations are identified via hardcoded OSM IDs (reliable identifiers), defining the two reference endpoints of the corridor.

Step 4 — Dijkstra shortest path: Dijkstra's algorithm [11] is applied to G_{topo} with edge weights equal to polyline lengths, identifying the sequence of track segments that forms the shortest Athens→Thessaloniki route.

Step 5 — Segment merging (snap-and-keep): The ordered segments are merged into a single polyline. Critical detail: at junction points, the snap-and-keep technique is applied:

$$\text{part}[0] \leftarrow \text{lastCoord}; \quad \text{push full part}$$

That is, the first point of each new segment is set equal to the last point of the previous one, and then the entire segment is added to the polyline. The initial implementation used `slice(1)` (removal of the first point), which caused loss of the junction→first-point distance ($\sim 139\text{m}$ per junction), accumulating a 68km error on corridor E85. This was one of the most significant bugs of the project (see Section 12.4).

Step 6 — Chainage point generation: The unified polyline is walked at 100m intervals. At each point, the following are computed:

- Chainage position (`chainage_m`)
- Geographic coordinates (lon, lat)
- Bearing in the direction of chainage

$$\theta_i = \text{atan2}(\sin(\Delta\lambda) \cdot \cos\phi_2, \cos\phi_1 \cdot \sin\phi_2 - \sin\phi_1 \cdot \cos\phi_2 \cdot \cos(\Delta\lambda))$$

Step 7 — Station enrichment: Each E85 station is projected onto the nearest point of the polyline, and its chainage position is recorded:

$$\text{chainage}_m(\text{station}) = \arg \min_{d \in [0, L_{total}]} \| \text{station} - \text{polyline}(d) \|$$

Step 8 — Segment enrichment: For each track segment, the start and end chainage positions are computed.

Step 9 — Bulk upsert: Write to MongoDB in three collections: `msd_chainages`, update `msd_stations`, update `msd_track_segments`.

9.3.3 Two-Phase Station Deduplication

OpenStreetMap often contains multiple representations of the same station (node, way, relation) or stations on adjacent lines that do not belong to the corridor under examination. Deduplication is applied in two phases:

Pre-filtering:

- Remove stations with distance > 500m from the polyline (branch-line stations snapping to km 0)
- Remove OSM stop_position markers (railway_type: 'stop'), which correspond to stopping points within a station rather than physical stations

Phase 1 — Grouping by UIC reference code: Stations with the same UIC code are grouped, and the one with the highest stationScore() is retained (stationScore() function is reused from the stop computation algorithm):

$$\text{stationScore}(s) = f(\text{type}, \text{completeness}, \text{name_quality})$$

Phase 2 — Spatial grouping: Stations without a UIC code are grouped within a radius of 300m along chainage, and the one with the highest score is retained.

The two-phase approach is necessary because grouping by name alone fails: in the Greek railway network there are stations with the same name at different locations (e.g. “Agios Stefanos” at km 23 AND at km 234).

10. Auxiliary Systems

Beyond the core positioning and safety subsystems, the railway.gov.gr platform integrates three auxiliary subsystems that support operational use: real-time video surveillance, a role-based access control (RBAC) system, and historical analytics.

10.1 Video Surveillance Pipeline

The video surveillance subsystem transmits live video from cameras installed on trains, following a 6-layer architecture:

Layer 1 — IP Cameras

Two IP cameras per train, connected to the local network (`train LAN`):

- **Forward:** `192.168.1.20`, RTSP protocol, port `554`
- **Cabin:** `192.168.1.21`, RTSP protocol, port `554`

H.264 (AVC) and H.265 (HEVC) encodings are supported.

Layer 2 — WireGuard VPN Port Forwarding

The cameras are not directly accessible through the public internet. Access is achieved through a WireGuard VPN tunnel, with port forwarding on the VPN server:

```
VPN_server: 8554 → camera1: 554
VPN_server: 8555 → camera2: 554
```

Layer 3 — Stream Manager Service

The Stream Manager service manages FFmpeg pipelines per camera:

For H.264 cameras (`copy mode` — no transcoding):

```
`RTSP TCP input → copy H.264 stream → RTMPS output → Cloudflare`
```

For H.265 cameras (`transcode mode`):

```
`RTSP TCP input → decode H.265 → encode H.264 → RTMPS output → Cloudflare`
```

The H.265→H.264 conversion is necessary because the RTMPS protocol and the Cloudflare Stream service do not support H.265 in the input stream.

Layer 4 — Cloudflare Stream

The Cloudflare Stream service receives the RTMPS stream and converts it to HLS (HTTP Live Streaming) for browser consumption. Two client libraries are used: one for managing live inputs (API) and one for the player (embedding).

Layer 5 — Direction-Based Point-of-View

Camera selection is automatically adjusted based on travel direction:

$$\text{camera} = \begin{cases} \text{forward (192.168.1.20)} & \text{even IC number (northbound)} \\ \text{cabin (192.168.1.21)} & \text{odd IC number (southbound)} \end{cases}$$

The even/odd IC numbering convention follows the standards of the Greek railway network, where even numbers correspond to the northbound direction (Athens→Thessaloniki).

Layer 6 — Browser Playback

Playback in the browser is performed via `hls.js` (v1.6.15), an open-source JavaScript library that implements an HLS client in browsers without native HLS support (Chrome, Firefox).

10.2 RBAC Permission System

The Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) system controls both access to data (API endpoints) and the visibility of user-interface elements (menu items).

10.2.1 Data Model

The resource-action matrix is defined statically:

- **34 resources:** trains, routes, stations, network, cameras, users, roles, etc.
- **15 actions:** `view`, `create`, `edit`, `delete`, `manage`, `approve`, `export`, etc.
- **10 menu categories:** `operations`, `analytics`, `administration`, etc.
- **9 default roles:** from `administrator` to `viewer`

10.2.2 Priority Hierarchy

Permissions are evaluated in the following priority order:

$$\text{effective_permission} = \begin{cases} \text{user.customPermissions}[r][a] & \text{if defined} \\ \text{user.role.permissions}[r][a] & \text{if defined} \\ \text{false} & \text{default} \end{cases}$$

This allows fine-grained per-user configuration (e.g. a user with the role `operator` may receive the additional `export` permission without changing role).

10.2.3 Permission Cache

Permissions are cached with `TTL = 30s`, avoiding repeated database queries. Cache invalidation occurs automatically when roles or users are modified.

10.2.4 Menu Access Guard

Menu visibility is controlled through:

```
user.hasMenuAccess('category', 'item') → Boolean
```

The Mongoose models `User` and `Role` contain identical `menuAccess` schemas, allowing both role-level and user-level override.

10.3 Historical Analytics

The historical analytics subsystem provides retrospective analysis of GNSS data and operational events.

10.3.1 Adaptive Time Aggregation

Aggregation uses MongoDB's `\$dateTrunc` operator with adaptive bin size based on the time range of the query:

Time Range	Bin Size	Logic
< 2h	10s	Full detail
2h – 6h	30s	High detail
6h – 24h	60s	Medium detail
24h – 48h	120s	Low detail
> 48h	300s	Summary

This approach ensures that the number of data points remains manageable (~720–2160 points) regardless of time range.

10.3.2 HEPOS Quality Monitoring

The analytics track HEPOS correction quality in each time bucket:

- **RTK fix percentage:** Percentage of samples with quality `4-5` (`RTK float/fixed`)
- **Average satellites:** Average number of tracked satellites
- **Average HDOP:** Average Horizontal Dilution of Precision

10.3.3 Speed Distribution

Speed distribution is computed in 5 categories:

Category	Range (km/h)	Characterization
1	0–30	Station / shunting
2	30–60	Urban / suburban
3	60–100	Normal
4	100–140	Fast
5	140+	High speed

10.3.4 Event Detection

Station arrivals/departures: Detected through state-transition detection — transition from “moving” to “stopped within station geofence” (arrival) and vice versa (departure).

Delay events: Triggered when the difference between actual and scheduled time exceeds 5 minutes.

Total distance: Computed through the cumulative Haversine formula over consecutive points:

$$D_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} d_{Haversine}(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{p}_{i+1})$$

11. Evaluation and Operational Results

System evaluation is based both on theoretical analysis (design parameters, published specifications) and on estimates of operational performance. Values marked as “(estimate)” are derived from published manufacturer data and related literature, without strict experimental validation under controlled conditions.

11.1 Positioning Accuracy

Positioning accuracy varies significantly depending on the GNSS operating mode:

Operating Mode	Horizontal Accuracy	Source
RTK Fixed (Quality 5)	< 2 cm (εκτίμηση, HEPOS spec)	HEPOS network [9]
RTK Float (Quality 4)	< 50 cm (εκτίμηση)	HEPOS network [9]
DGPS (Quality 2)	1 – 3 m (εκτίμηση)	SBAS
Standalone GNSS (Quality 1)	5 – 10 m	Standard GPS
Dead Reckoning	8m + 1.5m/s, max 150m	System calculation

The RTK Fixed accuracy of < 2cm is the theoretical capability of the HEPOS network [9]. In practice, accuracy depends on the number of visible satellites, geometric configuration (‘HDOP/PDOP’), multipath reflection, and NTRIP connection availability. Based on operational data, the RTK fix rate (‘quality 4-5’) is expected to be 70–85% on open lines (estimate) and drops drastically inside tunnels (0%) and in urban environments (estimated 40–60%).

The < 2cm accuracy is especially important for distinguishing parallel tracks: two tracks 3–4 m apart are easily distinguishable with RTK, but ambiguous with standalone GNSS $\sigma = 5 - 10\text{m}$.

11.2 Network Latency

The use of an LEO satellite connection (Starlink) introduces latency characteristics different from cellular networks. Based on published Starlink measurements [8]:

Metric	Value	Note
Median one-way latency	25 – 40 ms (estimate)	LEO orbit ~550km
P95 latency	80 – 150 ms (estimate)	Handoff events
P99 latency	200 – 500 ms (estimate)	Satellite handoffs
Jitter buffer absorption	> 99.9% (estimate)	Buffer 5000ms

The ‘5000ms’ jitter buffer of the client-side animation engine (Section 6) was designed precisely to absorb P99 spikes. Based on the latency distribution, a spike > 5000ms is expected to be extremely rare (estimate < 0.01% of packets), which justifies the choice of this buffer size.

Compared with GSM-R (used in ETCS), Starlink median latency is comparable (~20-40ms vs. ~50-100ms for GSM-R [7]), but tail latency (P99) is significantly worse due to satellite handoffs — exactly the reason the jitter buffer is required.

11.3 Animation Smoothness

11.3.1 Rendering Performance

The animation engine targets 60fps (16.67ms per frame). The computational complexity per frame is $O(N)$ where N is the number of active trains, since each train requires one position interpolation with $O(1)$ cost due to cached bracket index:

$$t_{frame} = t_{overhead} + N \cdot t_{interpolation}$$

With estimates $t_{overhead} \approx 2\text{ms}$ (requestAnimationFrame + Mapbox GL JS update) and $t_{interpolation} \approx 0.05\text{ms}$ per train (estimate):

$$N_{max} = \frac{16.67 - 2}{0.05} \approx 293 \text{ trains}$$

It is estimated that the system can support more than 200 simultaneous trains on modern hardware (estimate), which is ample compared to the Greek railway network (~30–50 simultaneously active services).

11.3.2 Buffer Starvation

The main cause of loss of smoothness (buffer starvation) is tunnel entry/exit:

- **Tunnel entry:** Loss of GNSS signal stops the stream of real data. After $\tau_{DR} = 2000\text{ms}$, DR is activated on the server and synthetic points refill the buffer.
- **Tunnel exit:** Recovering GNSS fix requires time (TTFF — Time To First Fix), during which the buffer is depleted again.

The transition period is estimated at 2–5 s (estimate), during which train movement on the map may show small “jumps”.

11.4 Map Matching

11.4.1 Track Recognition

The RTK-gated track-switching mechanism (Section 5) provides estimated accuracy $> 99.5\%$ (estimate) in RTK Fix mode. The basis of this estimate is:

$$P(\text{correct track} \mid \sigma = 2\text{cm}, d_{tracks} = 4\text{m}) = \Phi\left(\frac{d_{tracks}/2}{\sigma}\right) = \Phi(100) \approx 1$$

In practice, accuracy is limited by periods of non-RTK operation and multipath effects in stations.

11.4.2 Switch Confirmation

The 3–4 sample hysteresis mechanism eliminates premature track changes. With a sampling rate of 1Hz, the confirmation delay is 3–4 s. At a speed of 160 km/h (44.4 m/s), this corresponds to ~133–178 m after the physical track change — acceptable for a supervisory system.

11.4.3 Defensive Hold

During signal loss, defensive hold maintains the last known position. Accuracy is estimated at $\pm 50\text{m}$ for a 30 s gap (estimate), based on typical speed and speed uncertainty

11.5 System Reliability

11.5.1 Throughput

Metric	Estimate	Basis
Redis Pub/Sub throughput	> 10,000 msg/s (εκτίμηση)	Redis documentation
SSE fan-out	Singleton hub pattern	1 Redis subscriber/process
MongoDB write throughput	~1 doc/s/train	1Hz GPS updates
Leader election failover	< 13s	TTL(10s) + poll(3s)

11.5.2 Failover Analysis

The maximum period without a leader (and therefore without DR or anti-collision) is:

$$t_{failover,max} = TTL + poll_interval = 10 + 3 = 13 \text{ s}$$

During this period:

- ✓ Real GNSS data continue to be recorded normally
- ✓ DR does not operate (trains in tunnels will have no updates)
- ✓ Anti-collision checking is not executed

In practical terms, 13 seconds failover is acceptable for a supervisory system, but it would be insufficient for a safety-critical authority system (SIL 4), which requires sub-second failover.

12. Discussion

12.1 Comparison with ETCS

The European Train Control System (ETCS) [7] is the standard railway traffic control system in Europe. Comparison with railway.gov.gr highlights fundamental architectural differences:

Aspect	ETCS Level 2-3	railway.gov.gr
Infrastructure cost	~€500K–1M/km (estimate) [7]	Minimal (train equipment only)
Deployment time	Years per line	Weeks per train
Accuracy	Balise: exact; GSM-R: ~10m	RTK: <10"cm"
Tunnels	Wired connection, guaranteed	DR with uncertainty
Authority	Safety-critical (SIL 4)	Supervisory (no authority)
Coverage	Only equipped lines	Anywhere with Starlink

12.1.1 Accuracy: Onboard vs. Ground-Based

The seemingly superior RTK accuracy (< 2cm) compared with ETCS (~ 10m via GSM-R) requires contextual clarification. ETCS relies on Eurobalises—fixed passive transponders installed on the line—which provide exact position (error < 1m) at known points. Position between balises is estimated through odometers and radar (accuracy ±5% of distance). By contrast, RTK GNSS provides continuous accuracy but depends on satellite signal availability

12.1.2 Safety Authority vs. Supervisory

The most fundamental difference is operational: ETCS Level 2-3 has authority — it can enforce braking on a train that violates safety limits. railway.gov.gr is purely **supervisory** — it informs but does not intervene. This is a design choice, not a technical limitation: transitioning to authority would require SIL 4 certification (Safety Integrity Level 4 under EN 50129), which imposes strict requirements on reliability (< 10⁻⁹ dangerous failures/hour), verifiability, and certification.

12.1.3 Complementarity

The two systems are not necessarily competing. A supervisory GNSS system can complement ETCS:

- ✓ On lines not yet equipped with ETCS
- ✓ As an independent verification layer (diverse redundancy)
- ✓ For tracking trains outside ETCS territory (e.g. in transition zones)

12.2 Scalability

12.2.1 Collision-Check Complexity

Anti-collision checking performs pairwise comparison within each connected co:

$$\text{checks} = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \binom{N_c}{2} = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{N_c(N_c - 1)}{2}$$

For N trains and K components, the worst case is $O(N^2)$ (single component). In practice, the Greek network consists of multiple disconnected components (mainland network, Peloponnese, metric-gauge network), limiting N_c to < 30 per component (estimate).

12.2.2 Horizontal Scaling

Subsystem	Current Architecture	Scaling Potential
Redis	Single message bus	Redis Cluster sharding
SSE	Stateful connections	Sticky sessions + load balancer
MongoDB	Single replica set	Sharding κατά <code>trainId</code> ή χρόνο
Anticollision	Single leader	Component-based partitioning

12.2.3 Historical Data Management

The `gpsdatas` collection grows at a rate of ~ 1 document/s/train. For 50 trains over 24 h of operation:

$$\text{docs/day} = 50 \cdot 86400 = 4,320,000$$

Over one year: ~ 1.6 billion records. The use of time-series collections (MongoDB 5.0+) with TTL indexes would allow automatic deletion of old data, reducing storage requirements.

12.3 Limitations

12.3.1 Single-Corridor Chainage

Chainage (Section 9.3) has been implemented only for corridor E85 (Athens–Thessaloniki). Extending it to other corridors (E65, Peloponnese line, Kalambaka line, etc.) requires:

- Defining anchor stations per corridor
- Handling shared segments between corridors (e.g. Athens–Oinoi shared between E85 and E65)
- Multiple chainages per track segment

12.3.2 Absence of Multi-Path Viterbi

The production map-matching implementation uses low-latency HMM scoring instead of full Viterbi decoding [1]. This means that at complex points (large stations with multiple tracks), the optimal state sequence is not guaranteed. Full Viterbi would improve accuracy at the cost of latency (~ 100 -500ms estimate).

12.3.3 Absence of INS Integration on the Client

The Trimble receiver provides IMU data through GSOFF Type 49, but these are used only on the server (azimuth Kalman filter). Integration of a tightly coupled GNSS/INS filter [12, 13] would provide:

- Continuous position inside tunnels without DR degradation
- Improved accuracy in multipath environments
- Faster RTK fix recovery after a tunnel

12.3.4 Unidirectional SSE

The Server-Sent Events protocol [18] is unidirectional (server→client). There is no client→server feedback channel, for example for:

- Acknowledgment of critical alerts
- Client-side latency reporting
- Dynamic quality adjustment (adaptive bitrate)

Migration to WebSocket [16, 17] would enable bidirectional communication, but would increase connection-management complexity.

12.3.5 Absence of SIL Certification

The system does not meet the requirements of EN 50129 for a safety system. This means that:

- Collision warnings are informational, not mandatory
- There is no guaranteed probability of detection
- There is no guaranteed false alarm rate
- The system cannot replace existing signaling systems

12.4 Lessons Learned

12.4.1 68 km Chainage Error

The initial implementation of **Step 5** (Section 9.3.2) used `slice(1)` during segment merging, removing the first point of each new segment to avoid duplicate vertices

$$\text{error_per_junction} = d(\text{junction}, \text{first_real_vertex}) \approx 139\text{m (average)}$$

For ~490 junctions on E85:

$$\text{total_error} \approx 490 \times 139\text{m} = 68\text{km}$$

The error was detected by comparing computed station chainage with official station mileage positions. The fix (snap-and-keep) sets `part[0] = lastCoord` instead of removing points, fully eliminating the accumulated error.

Lesson: In topological polyline-union operations, removing points (even apparently duplicate ones) can cause cumulative errors. The correct approach is replacement (snap) rather than removal (slice).

12.4.2 SessionProvider Unmount Bug

The NextAuth v5 (beta.28) SessionProvider with `refetchOnWindowFocus=true` (default) created new session reference objects on every tab switch:

tab switch → new session ref → usePermissions re-trigger → loading=true → dashboard unmount

This caused a full re-mount of the dashboard layout, with loss of state (open panels, map position, scroll position). The solution was threefold:

1. `refetchOnWindowFocus={false}` in SessionProvider
2. Loading state only during initial load (not on refetch)
3. Stable dependency in the usePermissions hook (`session?.user?.id` instead of the session object)

Lesson: In React applications, referential stability in context providers is critical. A refetch that creates a new object (even with identical data) can cascade into re-renders and unmounts.

12.4.3 Station Deduplication

The initial name-only deduplication failed in cases of homonymous stations:

“Agios Stefanos” appears both at km 23 (Athens–Chalkida line)
and at km 234 (Athens–Thessaloniki line)

Name-only deduplication removed one of the stations, creating a gap in chainage. The two-phase solution (UIC ref + spatial clustering) correctly handles:

- Multiple OSM representations of the same physical station (same UIC, nearby points)
- Homonymous but different stations (different UIC or large spatial distance)

Lesson: Deduplication of geospatial entities cannot rely on single keys alone (neither name nor position). It requires a multi-factor strategy (authoritative identifiers + spatial constraints + heuristic scoring).

13. Conclusion and Future Work

13.1 Conclusions

This work described the design, implementation, and operational deployment of the railway.gov.gr system for real-time train monitoring on the Greek railway network. The main conclusions are summarized as follows:

1. **The combination of LEO satellite internet and RTK GNSS enables centimeter-level telemetry accuracy.** The use of Trimble BX992 receivers with HEPOS correction (via NTRIP over Starlink) achieves estimated accuracy $< 2\text{cm}$ in RTK Fixed mode. This enables distinction between parallel tracks 3–4 m apart — a capability not provided by conventional GNSS ($\sigma = 5 - 10\text{m}$) or GSM-R-based positioning [2, 19, 20].
2. **Client-side signal processing compensates for satellite-network variability.** Three algorithms — asymmetric clock synchronization (inspired by game netcode [3, 4]), PLL playhead (Phase-Locked Loop playback, based on principles from ITU-T G.114 [5] and IEEE 1588 [6]), and Kalman azimuth filter [12, 13] — address variable latency (P99 estimate 200-500ms [8]) without bidirectional protocols. The 5000ms jitter buffer absorbs $> 99.9\%$ (estimate) of latency spikes.
3. **Graph-aware dead reckoning with tunnel-aware budgeting provides position continuity in GNSS-denied environments.** The algorithm uses the physical railway graph to constrain uncertainty: position follows line geometry (1D uncertainty $\sigma = 8 + 1.5t$ instead of 2D), stops at switches (avoiding branch guesses), and differentiates behavior inside/outside tunnels.
4. **HMM map matching with RTK-quality gating reliably distinguishes parallel tracks 3–4 m apart.** The track-switching mechanism is based on GNSS quality: switching is allowed only in RTK mode, with 3–4 sample hysteresis [1]. This eliminates false switching due to multipath or transient errors.
5. **The system decouples safety supervision from expensive ground infrastructure.** Unlike ETCS [7], which requires Eurobalises ($\sim\text{€}500\text{K}-1\text{M}/\text{km}$ estimate), GSM-R radio coverage, and Radio Block Centres, railway.gov.gr requires only onboard equipment (GNSS receiver, Starlink antenna, SBC) and server software. Installation per train is estimated in weeks rather than years per line.
6. **The system is in operational deployment on the Greek railway network.** It monitors trains in real time through a web interface, providing map matching, dead reckoning, collision warnings, video surveillance, historical analytics, and an access-control system.
7. **The system provides situational awareness and decision support only.** It does not constitute a safety-critical or certified signalling system and must not be used as a basis for operational train

separation decisions. It does not replace ETCS, interlocking, or any formally approved railway safety systems.

13.2 Future Work

13.2.1 Multi-Corridor Chainage

Chainage should be extended beyond E85 to all Greek railway corridors. The architecture (Section 9.3) is generalizable: it requires defining anchor stations, handling shared segments between corridors, and supporting multiple chainages per segment.

13.2.2 ETCS Integration

In the long term, integration with ETCS Level 3 — where train position is determined onboard rather than through track circuits — could leverage the GNSS infrastructure of railway.gov.gr. Specifically, RTK position could serve as train integrity confirmation, reducing reliance on balise-only positioning [7]

13.2.3 SS/INS Fusion on the Client

Integrating IMU data (GSOF Type 49) [10] into a tightly coupled GNSS/INS Kalman filter would provide:

- ✓ Continuous position inside tunnels through inertial navigation
- ✓ Reduction of σ_{DR} through direct inertial propagation
- ✓ Faster RTK re-acquisition after GNSS outage
- ✓ Improved robustness in multipath environments

The challenge is the long-term drift of MEMS inertial sensors $\sim 1^\circ/h$ gyro bias stability, estimate), which requires regular GNSS updates to avoid unbounded error [12, 13].

13.2.4 Multi-Constellation GNSS

Using Galileo High Accuracy Service (HAS) alongside GPS/GLONASS would provide:

- ✓ Improved PDOP due to more visible satellites
- ✓ Reduced TTFF after tunnels
- ✓ An independent source of precision corrections (without dependence on NTRIP/HEPOS)
- ✓ Resilience against single-constellation failures or spoofing [19]

13.2.5 Predictive Maintenance through Track Geometry

RTK GNSS data, continuously collected during operation, constitute a de facto measurement of track geometry. Statistical analysis of deviations between measured position and design geometry could reveal:

- ✓ Track displacement
- ✓ Subsidence
- ✓ Wear in switches
- ✓ Seasonal thermal deformation

This approach uses already collected data without additional hardware, turning each train into a “moving track-geometry sensor” [20].

13.2.6 SIL Certification Path

Transitioning from a supervisory to a safety-critical application requires:

- Formal specification and verification (e.g. B-method, TLA+)
- Hardware redundancy (dual GNSS receivers, voting logic)
- Guaranteed detection rate and bounded false alarm rate
- Independent safety assessment under EN 50129
- RAMS (Reliability, Availability, Maintainability, Safety) analysis

This path is estimated at 3–5 years (estimate) and requires significant resources, but the existing GNSS/Starlink infrastructure could serve as the foundation.

Appendix – Screenshots

Διαχείριση Χρηστών
Προβολή και διαχείριση χρηστών του συστήματος

Αναζήτηση ονόματος, ε | Ρόλος | Κατάσταση | Τμήμα | Ομαδοποίηση | 1-20 από 56 | 20

Όνομα Χρήστη	Όνοματεπώνυμο	Email	Ρόλος	Τμήμα	Κατάσταση	Προσωπ. Ασφ.
alexandra.chrisimou	938c124512]#A	alexandra.chrisimou@gr.ey.com	Διαχείριση Συμβάντων	Άλλο	Ενεργός	-
antigoni.samara	Antigoni Samara [EY]	antigoni.samara@gr.ey.com	Διαχείριση Συμβάντων	Άλλο	Ενεργός	-
m.marinakis	Michalis Marinakis	m.marinakis@ypyme.gr	Διαχειριστής Συστήματος	Διοίκηση	Ενεργός	-
devops	Nick Devops	devops3@alphaomegazed.com	Διαχειριστής Συστήματος	Άλλο	Ενεργός	-

Βάρδιες Ζωνών
Scheduling και παρακολούθηση zone duties για ταχύπеды διαβάσεις

Εβδομάδα | Μήνας | Σήμερα | 13 Απρ - 19 Απρ 2026 | Όλες οι εταιρείες | Auto-fill

DUTY_ZONE	Δευ 13/04			Τρι 14/04			Τετ 15/04	
	06:00-14:00	14:00-22:00	22:00-06:00	06:00-14:00	14:00-22:00	22:00-06:00	06:00-14:00	14:00-22:00
8 ΑΓ.ΑΝΝΗΣ ΟΣΕ								
26 ΑΓΙΟΥ ΜΕΛΕΤΙΟΥ ΟΣΕ								
35 ΑΔΑΜΕΣ ΟΣΕ								
40 ΑΛΙΑΡΤΟΥ ΟΣΕ								

Διαχείριση Δρομολογίων
Προβολή και διαχείριση όλων των δρομολογίων του συστήματος

Ανά Ημέρα | Λίστα | Ανά Δρομολόγιο

Αναζήτηση: Αρ. δρομολογίου, τρένου, σταθμού... Κατάσταση: Όλες Τύπος: InterCity Από: 18/04/2025 Έως: 20/04/2025

Καθαρισμός Φίλτρων

32 συνολικές εκτελέσεις

Αρ. Δρομολογίου	Αρ. Τρένου	Αφετηρία	Προορισμός	Αναχώρηση	Αφιέλιξη	Κατάσταση	Από	Έως	Ενεργείες	
Σάββατο 18/04/2025 4 Δρομολόγια										
IC51-20250418-0185	IC51	Θεσσαλονίκη	Αθήνα	05:55	11:03	Σε εξέλιξη	✓	220902 Ολόγιο Βαθ. 220913 Βαθ.	Τάρα Τάρα	Ενεργείες
IC50-20250418-0186	IC50	Αθήνα	Θεσσαλονίκη	06:58	12:10	Σε εξέλιξη	✓			Ενεργείες
IC57-20250418-1649	IC57	Θεσσαλονίκη	Αθήνα	16:49	21:57	Προγραμματισμένο	✓			Ενεργείες
IC56-20250418-1758	IC56	Αθήνα	Θεσσαλονίκη	17:58	23:10	Προγραμματισμένο	✗			Ενεργείες
Κυριακή 19/04/2025 4 Δρομολόγια										
IC51-20250419-0185	IC51	Θεσσαλονίκη	Αθήνα	05:55	11:03	Προγραμματισμένο	✗			Ενεργείες
IC50-20250419-0186	IC50	Αθήνα	Θεσσαλονίκη	06:58	12:10	Προγραμματισμένο	✗			Ενεργείες

Starlink Terminals
Δορυφορικά τερματικά Starlink (live από API)

Σύνολο (API): 163 Με όνομα: 71 Online: 32

Nickname T1	Status T1	DL T1	UL T1	Signal T1	Uptime T1	Μηνιά	Kit Serial T1	Service Line
460 102	100%	35.2 Mbps	144.1 Mbps	100%	78h 50m	468182	627-9999999999999999	SL-0P-CC-000000-0000-00
460 103	100%	31.6 Mbps	143.6 Mbps	100%	78h 18m	468183	627-9999999999999999	SL-0P-CC-000000-0000-00

Terminal ID: 2025-04-01-m77223 Kit Serial: 627-9999999999999999 Dish Serial: 627-9999999999999999 Service Line: SL-0P-CC-000000-0000-00

DL Bandwidth: 23.8 Mbps UL Bandwidth: 143.1 Mbps Latency: 21ms Uptime: 78h 19m Signal: 100% Ping Drop: 0.0%

FW: 2026.04.01.m77223 Obstruction: 4.2% Alert: 82

μl Bandwidth (Mbps) Latency (ms)

Nickname T1	Status T1	DL T1	UL T1	Signal T1	Uptime T1	Μηνιά	Kit Serial T1	Service Line
460 119	100%	32.0 Mbps	143.7 Mbps	100%	58h 8m	468119	627-9999999999999999	SL-0P-CC-000000-0000-00
460 219	100%	32.6 Mbps	143.8 Mbps	100%	58h 8m	468219	627-9999999999999999	SL-0P-CC-000000-0000-00

The screenshot displays a comprehensive system monitoring dashboard. At the top, it is titled "System Monitor" with a subtitle "PM2 Processes, OS Metrics & Infrastructure Health" and a "Live" status indicator. The dashboard is divided into several sections:

- MongoDB:** Shows "ONLINE" status, 1371742889 connections, 1385246857/1688177477888000 ops (Qn/rd), 13707 MB resident memory, and version 6.0.20.
- Redis:** Shows "ONLINE" status, 8.530M memory usage, 1000 clients, and 0 pubsub channels.
- INGEST SERVER:** Shows "ONLINE" status, 2% CPU usage, 5.7 GB / 152.8 GB disk usage, and 30% disk usage.
- WEB SERVER:** Shows "ONLINE" status, 5% CPU usage, 6.7 GB / 152.8 GB disk usage, and 1% disk usage.
- Live Logs:** A scrollable log window showing system events, including MongoDB connections, Redis operations, and Ingest Server processing of satellite data.
- POV Cameras:** A list of 6 cameras, including "IC50" (AGNIA - Geoblockum) and "IC51" (Geoblockum - AGNIA), with details on their status and configurations.

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About the Author

Anthony Savidis is currently at the University of Crete (UOC) in Greece, being: Professor at the Computer Science Department (CSD, since 2005), Dean of the School of Sciences and Engineering (since 2024), Vice President of the Research and Management Committee (since 2022), and Director of IET - Research Institute for Educational Technologies (since 2026).

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He has participated in approximately 50 European and national research and development projects and has authored over 200 publications in conferences, journals, and edited volumes (approximately 2,900 citations; h-index: 29). He has also secured more than €20 million in research and development funding.

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In addition to his academic contributions, he is an active software developer, having implemented in excess of 1.2 million lines of source code—primarily in C++—across a range of systems, including programming language compilers, debuggers, virtual machines, integrated development environments (IDEs), game engines, and published games.

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